

D4.5 Guidelines on Financing CE projects

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Summary

This report focuses on the financing options for the B-WaterSmart project, which includes six demonstration projects of circular solutions in water management. Financing is crucial for scaling and disseminating these solutions. LLs within the project propose ways to create and distribute value in circular business ecosystems, and a review of green financing options was conducted to support these efforts.

The review examines financing products, services, and instruments for CE projects in the water sector, particularly in Europe. It highlights the importance of economic policies in promoting a circular economy and defines this concept within the water sector, emphasising sustainable water management practices like reuse and recycling.

Overall, the report details significant advancements in green financing in the water sector, aiding sustainable development and promoting new business models.

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Dissemination level

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- PP = Restricted to other programme participants
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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

3Ts' - Tariffs, taxes and transfers

AdP - Águas de Portugal

ALFI - Association of the Luxembourg Fund Industry

ARERA - The Italian Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks and Environment

CAPEX - Capital expenditures

CE - Circular Economy

COW - Condensate of Whey

CSA - Coordination & Support Actions

DG CLIMA - Directorate-General for Climate Action

DWS - Deutsche Asset Management

EBA - European Banking Authority

EC - Electrochlorination

EIB - European Investment Bank

EIC - Europe Innovation Council

EIOPA - European Insurance and Occupational Pensions Authority

EJP - European Joint Programme

ERDF - European Regional Development Fund

ESG - Environmental, Social and Governance

ESG ETFs - ESG Exchange-Traded Funds

ESMA - European Securities and Markets Authority

ETS - Emissions Trading System

EU - European Union

EUGBS - European green bond standard

FAQ - Frequently Asked Questions

GHG - Greenhouse Gases

IA - Innovation Actions

IF - Innovation Fund

LL - Living Lab

NaClO - Sodium hypochlorite

Nat cat - Natural catastrophes

NCP - National contact points

NGO - Non-Governmental Organisation

OECD - Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

PCP - Pre-Commercial Procurement
PENSAARP - Plan for Water Supply and Wastewater and Rainwater Management
PERTE - Strategic Projects for Economic Recovery and Transformation
PPI - Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions
PPP - Public-Private Partnership
RoC - Return of circularity
RIA - Research & Innovation Actions
SDGs - Sustainable Development Goals
SED - Selective Electrodialysis
SFDR - Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation
SIB - Social Impact Bond
SMEs - Small and medium-sized enterprises
TEG - Technical Expert Group
TRL - Technology Readiness Levels
UASB - Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket
UNEP FI - United Nations Environment Programme's Financial Initiative
WFD - Water Framework Directive
WICER - Water in Circular Economy and Resilience
WWTP - Wastewater treatment plant

Revision history

The table below provides detailed explanations of the integration of the changes requested as part of the final project review.

Received feedback	How feedback was integrated in D4.5	Affected Section
The executive summary shall be reviewed as it rather stands as an introduction. What are the key points to highlight and communicate to the audience who will read the document?	<p>The executive summary has been restructured and rewritten to address the reviewer's comments. The opening paragraph now clearly outlines the report's purpose and scope, immediately followed by a concise methodology section to provide context. Key findings are prominently highlighted early in the summary, ensuring that the main points are clearly communicated to the reader.</p> <p>Summaries of each Living Lab have been incorporated into the main body of the executive summary. These, now provide specific examples of circular economy approaches in water management across Europe, offering valuable insights into the practical applications of the project's findings.</p>	Executive Summary (entire section)
What is the relevance of the statement on page 10, linked to the young population and energy?	The statement on page 10 addresses the role of younger generations in driving sustainability and energy transitions, which aligns with the goals of CE projects in the water sector. This is further explained in the paragraph.	Section 1- partially
What is it meant by "financial system" on page 14?	An introductory definition of financial systems is included in the section 2.2	Section 2.2 - partially
What is the rationale of section 2 in relation to the topic addressed in the deliverable? Establishing some links would be useful.	An introduction to section 2 has been included to link it to the rest of the report.	Section 2- introduction
An analysis of how "public financing institutions play a crucial role in providing financial support for circular economy projects in the water sector" should be added. The report does not sufficiently develop on this topic	An additional paragraph has been included in section 2.4 (sustainable finance strategies) that connects the EU strategy with the role of public financing in supporting the transition to CE. In addition, section 4.1.1 emphasises this	Section 2.4

	topic.	
<p>Section 4 should be reviewed to be more specific and focus on the financial instruments that will support either the development of CE projects, or CE innovations. The general list should be put in an Annex.</p> <p>Another question is: do the existing financial instruments sufficiently support the development and deployment of CE projects and innovations? It would be an interesting question to tackle, because it might not be the case, despite all the available funding and financial instruments.</p> <p>Section 4.2.1 is interesting and could be further expanded to briefly assess how CE projects and innovations are rated in terms of risks.</p>	<p>Section 4 has been amended accordingly:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i) described instruments focus on CE projects and innovation; ii) the general list of instruments and their eligibility and application process has been moved to Annex I iii) An analysis of current penetration of financing instruments in CE has not been included, since it would require a specific assessment, outside the scope of the task. However, more specific figures about investments and numbers have been included in section 4. iv) 	<p>Section 4- partially and development of Annex I.</p>
<p>The report should expand on whether the LLs are able to access national funding (beyond Germany) and/or EU funding, and whether they are willing to do so to expand the projects. To what extent, for instance, could the NextGenerationEU be tapped into?</p>	<p>Specific interviews were carried out to each LL representative individually, in order to understand the requested detail and all information related to local financial options.</p> <p>Additional details have been included in the report, including a summary of the financing gaps assessment for each LL.</p>	<p>Section 5 has been upgraded and Section 5.7 created.</p>
<p>The report should provide 10 key guidelines to access financing for CE projects, to reflect the title of the deliverable.</p>	<p>Several guidelines are included in the report to access financing instruments to develop CE projects and examples of real cases are explained as well.</p>	<p>N/A</p>

Executive summary

This deliverable presents a comprehensive overview of financing options for circular economy (CE) initiatives within the B-WaterSmart project, which aims to develop innovative water management solutions across six European Living Labs (LLs). The primary objective of this report is to identify and analyse funding mechanisms that support the transition to a circular economy, particularly in the water sector, aligned with the European Green Deal and the EU's sustainability goals.

The study utilises a mixed-methods approach, combining a literature review, financial data analysis, and stakeholder interviews to assess the financing landscape for CE projects. It highlights the critical role of both public and private financial institutions in providing resources for sustainable water projects. Key financial instruments, including grants, green bonds, and Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs), are examined for their suitability to support CE innovations.

The **key findings** of the deliverable can be summarised as follows:

- **Role of Public Financing:** Public financing institutions, such as the European Investment Bank (EIB) and Horizon Europe, are crucial for advancing CE projects by providing grants, loans, and risk-sharing mechanisms. However, there is a notable gap in private sector investment due to perceived risks and regulatory uncertainties.
- **Opportunities in Sustainable Finance:** The growing sustainable finance market, especially green bonds and Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG)-focused funds, offers significant opportunities for water sector projects. Nevertheless, aligning these financial products with water-specific requirements remains challenging.
- **Importance of Financial Structuring:** CE projects benefit from a diverse mix of funding sources. Effective financial structuring—such as leveraging blended finance and PPPs—can attract more private capital by balancing risk and return perspectives.

Living Labs Overview:

1. **Alicante, Spain:** Focuses on transforming wastewater treatment plants into biofactories, using Selective Electrodialysis and electrochlorination to valorize brine and recover resources. This project demonstrates substantial potential for reducing environmental impact through wastewater reuse.
2. **Lisbon, Portugal:** Addresses water scarcity by implementing reclaimed water solutions for urban and industrial use. The pilot project emphasizes safe water reuse to support urban irrigation, thereby reducing the dependency on freshwater resources.
3. **East Frisia, Germany:** Targets industrial water reuse in the dairy sector, using advanced filtration and disinfection methods to treat whey water. This initiative showcases circular economy principles within an industrial framework.
4. **Bodø, Norway:** Explores waste-to-energy solutions, particularly through biogas production from sludge co-digestion. This LL highlights the integration of waste management and energy recovery in a circular economy model.

5. **Flanders, Belgium:** Aims to enhance water reuse in agriculture by collecting and treating stormwater for subirrigation, improving groundwater resilience. This project illustrates the potential for CE practices in agricultural water management.
6. **Venice, Italy:** Implements resource recovery strategies for reclaimed water and nutrient recycling in an urban context. This LL focuses on adapting CE solutions to the complex water management needs of a historic coastal city.

To further advance CE financing, the report proposes ten key guidelines to improve access to funding. These include strengthening public-private partnerships, tailoring financial instruments to CE projects, harmonizing policy frameworks across EU member states, and improving the visibility of project benefits. It also underscores the need to align financing strategies with local contexts to enhance investment appeal.

In conclusion, the report emphasizes the transformative potential of CE financing for water projects in Europe. While public funding remains essential, private capital can be mobilized by developing innovative financing structures and demonstrating the multifaceted benefits of circular water management. The European Union is well-positioned to lead this transition by fostering collaboration between policy, finance, and technology sectors, contributing to sustainable water use, resource efficiency, and economic resilience.

1 Introduction

Climate change is not only real, but it also represents the most severe threat to the global economy. The scientific community has been warning about this crisis for over 45 years, emphasising that the sooner we prepare, the less we will suffer. The impacts of climate change on human life include forced migrations, premature deaths, increased extreme poverty, and food insecurity. In the next decade, six out of ten risks will be environmental (Figure 1), and the future competitiveness will depend on the readiness to face this imminent crisis.

Figure 1. Global risks ranked by severity over the short and long term (source: World Economic Forum Global Risks Perception Survey 2022-2023)

Simultaneously, the world is already undergoing a transition to a low-emission model, a trend accelerated by the pandemic. It is crucial to observe where capital is flowing, as this will indicate future economic trends. In the next six years, an investment of over 30 trillion dollars is expected in the green economy, led by Asia and the Middle East (Table 1). Green bonds have experienced exponential growth, with companies leading this revolution more than governments. Firms like BlackRock have started divesting from companies without a sustainable vision, showing that this movement is perceived as a significant economic opportunity (IFC World Bank, 2022). Green companies not only show better stock market performance compared to non-green companies but

also recover better from crises such as COVID-19. Additionally, a regulatory wave is approaching, which will require all companies to meet strict sustainability requirements.

Table 1. Investment potential by region and sector until 2030

	Waste	Renewable Energy	Public Transport	Climate-Smart Water	Electric Vehicles	Green Construction	Total
East Asia and the Pacific	\$ 82 Billion	\$ 266 Billion	\$ 135 Billion	\$ 461 Billion	\$ 569 Billion	\$ 16 Trillion	\$ 17,5 Trillion
South Asia	\$ 22 Billion	\$ 141 Billion	\$ 217 Billion	\$ 110 Billion	\$ 214 Billion	\$ 1,8 Trillion	\$ 2,5 Trillion
Europe and Central Asia	\$ 17 Billion	\$ 88 Billion	\$ 116 Billion	\$ 64 Billion	\$ 46 Billion	\$ 881 Billion	\$ 1,2 Trillion
Middle East and North Africa	\$ 28 Billion	\$ 31 Billion	\$ 281 Billion	\$ 79 Billion	\$ 133 Billion	\$ 1,1 Trillion	\$ 1,7 Trillion
Sub-Saharan Africa	\$ 13 Billion	\$ 89 Billion	\$ 159 Billion	\$ 101 Billion	\$ 344 Billion	\$ 768 Billion	\$ 1,5 Trillion
Latin America and the Caribbean	\$ 37 Billion	\$ 226 Billion	\$ 109 Billion	\$ 228 Billion	\$ 285 Billion	\$ 4,1 Trillion	\$ 5 Trillion
	\$ 200 Billion	\$ 842 Billion	\$ 1 Trillion	\$ 1 Trillion	\$ 1,6 Trillion	\$ 24,7 Trillion	\$ 29,4 Trillion

Source: IFC World Bank (2022)

Economic recovery plans and the current global geopolitical situation present a significant opportunity to build a new economic model that is more sustainable, just, and equitable. Young people increasingly recognise the importance of sustainability and prefer to work for companies that uphold these principles (Figure 2). A majority of young people believe it is crucial to offer more sustainable products and, when given the choice, prefer green options. The growing emphasis on sustainability among younger generations impacts the investment landscape, as both public institutions and private investors respond to this demographic’s preferences. This societal shift accelerates the adoption of green technologies, including those used in circular water management¹. By tapping into this trend, CE projects can gain broader support, especially in areas where energy efficiency and resource sustainability are key, aligning with the values that drive younger generations.

Figure 2. Importance of sustainability credentials when attracting and retaining talent (Source: Anthesis Group, 2023)

¹ World Economic Forum, 2023. Global Shapers Community Annual Report 2023-2024 <https://weforum.org/publications/global-shapers-community-annual-report-2023-2024/>

Energy security is closely tied to the energy transition, and conflicts like the one between Russia and Ukraine have exposed our vulnerabilities. However, funds such as the Next Generation EU can help position countries as energy leaders if they are utilised effectively. This new economic model is built on three fundamental pillars: Planet, People, and Profit, with a long-term perspective.

As a result of Task T4.4, which identified potential funding sources for projects aimed at promoting a circular economy, this deliverable (D4.5) will conduct a comprehensive review of these funding options. The analysis will cover their relevance, accessibility, and potential impact on advancing circular economy initiatives.

The transition to a circular economy, which seeks to maximise resource reuse and minimise waste, requires the adoption of innovative technologies. To develop and implement these technologies effectively, appropriate funding strategies are essential. This deliverable provides a crucial roadmap for identifying and leveraging various funding sources, including private investments, government grants, green loans, and crowdfunding. In addition to outlining the available options and investments made in recent years, it offers practical recommendations for businesses and research centres to access the necessary funds to drive technological projects that facilitate this transition.

The document aims to compile all available funding sources for circular economy solutions in Europe, categorised by type of support, project phase, and technology readiness level (TRL), thereby serving as a guide for developing these technologies.

The objective is to provide a strategic framework that stakeholders can use to secure financial support for projects contributing to a sustainable and circular economic model.

Furthermore, this review will consider regional specificities and the unique characteristics of each Living Lab (LL). Interviews were conducted to gather information on their current funding, the resources needed to scale technologies, and local funding options.

2 Background: the financial system, climate change, and circular economy initiatives

This section sets the foundation for exploring financing options for CE projects by examining the financial system's role in combating climate change (2.1) and presenting a conceptual framework of global and European policies for climate action (2.2). This framework underpins the development of European economic policy instruments (2.3) and strategies (2.4) that enable CE initiatives. By highlighting the relevance of these policy frameworks, the section underscores how the transition to a circular economy serves as a strategic response to one of society's most pressing challenges: climate change

2.1. The financial system and climate change

The Financial System is understood as the network of institutions, markets, regulations and instruments that collectively facilitate the allocation of capital within an economy. For the context of CE in the water sector, the system includes banks, investment funds, public financing bodies like the European Investment Bank, and other entities that provide capital for project development. The instruments used to allocate the investments are also included in the system.

Climate change-related risks in the financial sector have grown in importance, particularly since the 2015 Paris Agreement and the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The Paris Agreement aims to limit global temperature rise to well below 2°C, ideally to 1.5°C, above pre-industrial levels. Exceeding these limits could lead to more frequent and severe climatic events (e.g., storms, floods) and long-term structural changes such as rising sea levels, known as physical risks.

To meet the Paris Agreement's goals, the economy must become climate neutral. This involves enhancing adaptability to climate impacts, promoting low greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions development, securing necessary financing for sustainable growth, and compensating for any remaining impacts that cannot be reduced. This transformation carries "transition risks" related to policy, technology, and consumer preference changes. These risks are interconnected, as delayed or disorderly action can increase both physical and transition risks.

The European Green Deal, presented by the European Commission in 2019, aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050, requiring substantial investment. The Sustainable Europe Investment Plan, introduced in January 2020, seeks to mobilise at least €1 trillion in public and private investment over the next decade, with an additional €260 billion annually needed to meet 2030 climate and energy targets (European Commission, 2023).

The financial system is crucial in this transformation, channelling resources and developing sustainable financing instruments with necessary standardisation and transparency. Recent public and private initiatives aim to better understand climate change implications and establish frameworks for mobilising the required resources for this transition.

Figure 3. Natural catastrophes (nat cat) loss events in the first half of 2023 (Source: Munich Re, NatCatSERVICE, July 2023)

2.2. Global collaboration for Climate Change Action

The signing of the Paris Agreement and the adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as part of the 2030 Agenda in 2015 marked the beginning of concerted efforts in both the public and private sectors to mobilise financial resources to support the transition to sustainability and achieve the net zero goal. Several global initiatives stand out, some led by public entities and others by the private sector. These include the work of the G-20, the International Platform on Sustainable Finance, and the Coalition of Finance Ministers for Climate Action, as well as the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures. These initiatives aim to integrate climate risks into financial decision-making and promote disclosure of climate-related information. Additionally, international bodies such as the United Nations Environment Programme's Financial Initiative (UNEP FI) have worked collaboratively with the global financial sector to mobilise private financing for sustainable development. Moreover, the participation of central banks and financial supervisors, such as the Network of Central Banks and Supervisors for Greening the Financial System, in integrating climate and environmental considerations into financial supervision and monetary policy is noteworthy.

Figure 4. Timeline of the main global initiatives in sustainable finance (Source: Adapted from Banco de España, 2021)

2.3. Economic policy Instruments and the circular economy

The transition towards a circular economy is a prominent environmental objective outlined in the European Union's Green Deal, introduced in December 2019. This comprehensive plan addresses the urgent challenges of climate change, environmental degradation, and biodiversity loss, while also promoting economic growth and fostering inclusivity. The Green Deal is envisioned as a long-term

transformative agenda spanning several decades, with a key goal of achieving climate neutrality in the EU by 2050.

The circular economy dimension of the Green Deal aims to shift away from the conventional linear model of production and consumption, characterised by a take-make-dispose approach, towards regenerative systems that eliminate waste and pollution from the production process. This encompasses various areas such as resource efficiency, waste management, product design, extended producer responsibility, and market incentives.

Figure 5. Diagram of the circular economy (Source: Ellen MacArthur Foundation, February 2019)

To support the development of circular economy projects, the EU has established several financing mechanisms and initiatives aimed at mobilising public and private investment. At the core of the regulatory framework is the EU Taxonomy Regulation (EU 2020/852)² for sustainable activities. This regulation serves as a classification system, based on robust scientific methodology, which provides a common framework across the Union for defining economically sustainable activities with strong environmental credentials. The taxonomy plays a crucial role in the sustainable finance agenda by guiding investments towards validated green initiatives. Additionally, Regulation 2021/2139 introduced an industry-specific technical framework that outlines the sustainability screening standards companies and institutions must adhere to in order to be recognized as green and eligible for favourable financing.

² Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088. Available online at: [2020/852 - EN - taxonomy regulation - EUR-Lex](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/852/oj)

In the realm of water protection, circular economy projects must also comply with the EU's Water Framework Directive (WFD)³, which aims to achieve good ecological status for inland water bodies, transitional and coastal surface water, and groundwaters. The WFD employs individual pollutant regulations and water quality standards to ensure an integrated approach to water management within the EU. Furthermore, the Urban Waste Water Treatment Directive⁴ and the Sewage Sludge Directive⁵ are relevant for circular economy projects in the water sector, as they provide guidelines and requirements for the treatment of urban wastewater and sewage sludge, both of which are integral to circularity initiatives. While primarily targeting member states and their water management authorities, adhering to the objectives and principles of these EU Directives can help businesses involved in circular economy projects ensure compliance with environmental standards.

Figure 6. Status of Adoption of the Third RBMP⁶ in EU 27 - Last Update: December 20, 2023 (Source: European Commission, December 2023)

2.4. European Commission's sustainable finance strategy

The European Commission defines sustainable finance as the process of integrating environmental and social considerations into investment decisions, leading to increased investment in sustainable and long-term activities. Developing a strategy in this area within the European Union is a priority action of the European Commission's Capital Markets Union. It is also a key step in implementing the Paris Agreement and the EU's sustainable development agenda.

³ Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy. Available online at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2000/60/oj>

⁴ Council Directive 91/271/EEC of 21 May 1991 concerning urban waste-water treatment. Available online at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31991L0271>

⁵ Council Directive 86/278/EEC of 12 June 1986 on the protection of the environment, and in particular of the soil, when sewage sludge is used in agriculture. Available online at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31986L0278>

⁶ "State of play of 3rd RBMP adoption in EU 27" refers to the current status of adoption of the third River Basin Management Plan in all 27 EU member states, as part of the EU Water Framework Directive aiming to safeguard and enhance water quality in Europe

To contribute to this process, the European Commission established a High-Level Expert Group⁷ in 2016, comprising members from civil society, the financial sector, academia, and various European and international institutions. The group's final report⁸, published in January 2018, formed the basis of the action plan on sustainable finance (financing sustainable growth)⁹, which the Commission adopted in March 2018 and has been working on since.

The objective of this Action Plan is to develop the EU's strategy on sustainable finance and integrate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) issues into the European financial system. The three main objectives are: redirecting capital flows towards sustainable investments, managing risks related to climate change and environmental degradation, and promoting transparency and a long-term vision of economic and financial activity. To achieve these objectives, the Action Plan outlines ten key actions that can be divided into three categories (reorienting capital flows towards a more sustainable economy; mainstreaming sustainability into risk management; fostering transparency and long-termism) (Directorate-General for Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union, 2020).

The European Commission created a Technical Expert Group (TEG) in 2018 to advise on some of these actions. Specifically, the TEG provided guidance on developing a taxonomy of sustainable activities (EU taxonomy), methodologies for climate indices, corporate disclosure of climate-related information, and an EU Green Bond Standard. Based on this work, the Commission has developed regulations on the classification of environmentally sustainable activities or taxonomy, climate indices, and disclosure of sustainability-related information (Directorate-General for Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union, 2018).

In addition to regulatory efforts, the Commission has proposed the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive to enhance ESG reporting requirements. Furthermore, the European Commission presented a proposal for a European green bond standard (EUGBS)¹⁰ in July 2021, based on a voluntary framework aligned with the taxonomy, characterised by transparency, external review, and supervision by the European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA) (Directorate-General for Financial Stability, Financial Services and Capital Markets Union, 2021).

The European Banking Authority (EBA), the ESMA, and the European Insurance and Occupational Pensions Authority (EIOPA) have been called upon to provide guidance on integrating sustainability issues into legislation and identifying gaps. The EBA will evaluate whether differentiated prudential treatment related to environmental or social objectives is justified.

These efforts are part of the European Commission's broader strategy, including the Renewed Sustainable Finance Strategy, aimed at creating a framework for private investors and the public sector to contribute to sustainability and enhancing the resilience of the financial sector. This strategy is a component of the European Green Deal, which aims to make Europe climate-neutral by 2050

⁷ High-Level Expert Group on sustainable finance (HLEG). Available online at: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/publications/high-level-expert-group-sustainable-finance-hleg_en

⁸ Full report available online at: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/document/download/2e65cb1e-bd47-4441-816a-d89ec61eef45_en?filename=180131-sustainable-finance-final-report_en.pdf

⁹ More information about this action plan available online at: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/publications/renewed-sustainable-finance-strategy-and-implementation-action-plan-financing-sustainable-growth_en

¹⁰ The European green bond standard – Supporting the transition. Available online at: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/tools-and-standards/european-green-bond-standard-supporting-transition_en

through various measures, including the Sustainable Europe Investment Plan¹¹ and the Next Generation EU programme¹².

Figure 7. Next Generation EU: Total Funding Allocation (Source: FI Group, 2021)

The Sustainable Financing Strategy plays an essential role in financing circular economy (CE) projects in the water sector, particularly through public financing institutions, as these projects often require substantial upfront investment and involve higher levels of risk. Institutions such as the European Investment Bank (EIB), and public financing instruments such as Horizon Europe, and the LIFE Programme provide critical funding and support mechanisms that enable the development and scaling of CE initiatives. By offering low-interest loans, grants, and risk-sharing instruments, these institutions make it feasible to implement innovative technologies like water reuse, waste-to-energy solutions, and nutrient recovery systems. Public financing institutions are also instrumental in fostering public-private partnerships, leveraging private capital by mitigating financial risks and attracting a diversified pool of investors. Additionally, they align their funding strategies with EU sustainability goals and regulations, such as the European Green Deal and the EU Taxonomy for sustainable activities. This alignment not only helps to streamline the financing of CE projects but also ensures that such projects contribute to broader environmental and social objectives. As a result, public financing institutions are crucial in advancing the circular water economy, facilitating projects that might otherwise struggle to secure the necessary investment due to their complexity or innovative nature.

¹¹ Sustainable Europe Investment Plan: <https://www.iea.org/policies/12807-sustainable-europe-investment-plan>

¹² NextGenerationEU: https://next-generation-eu.europa.eu/index_en

2.5. Defining and classifying economic instruments

Financial instruments are the various tools and mechanisms used to allocate resources for project development. Each type has its own unique risk-reward profile and is designed to meet specific investment objectives. After reviewing several sources, it has been determined that these instruments can be broadly categorised into five main types:

i. Debt instruments. Debt instruments involve contractual agreements between borrowers and lenders, where the lender provides financial capital with the expectation of repayment over time, along with interest. These instruments can be accessed from public and private institutions and can be tailored to meet the needs of the parties involved. Aspects such as loan duration, interest rates, and repayment priority vary depending on the project's stage and characteristics. Senior and junior loans are important distinctions within debt instruments, differing in repayment priority and interest rates. Construction loans are relevant for water infrastructure projects, disbursing funds as construction stages are completed. Bonds, on the other hand, diverge structurally from loans and credit lines, as they are issued by borrowers and sold to institutional investors with the bank acting as an intermediary. Bonds offer recurring interest payments and repayment of principal at maturity. Their tradability in secondary markets makes them a flexible form of debt. Initiatives in sustainability and the circular economy may access green debt with more favourable financing conditions, such as green loans or debts, requiring project developers to certify environmental benefits. The European Investment Bank's (EIB) Water Financing Facility is an example of a relevant loan program in the EU, offering favourable borrowing conditions to public and private entities.

ii. Equity instruments. Equity involves the purchase of shares or ownership stakes in a project by investors, private or public. Equity investors become partial owners, sharing risks and benefits. Risks arise from fluctuations in asset value due to market trends or regulatory adjustments, while benefits come in the form of dividends or increases in project value. Equity investment typically has a long-term horizon and incentivizes active contribution of expertise, networks, and resources to support project growth. Equity shares can be traded on secondary markets, providing liquidity and tradability, enhancing attractiveness and potential returns on investment.

iii. Grants and subsidies. These non-repayable funds, often provided by governments, institutions, or NGOs, incentivize the adoption of sustainable practices. Grants and subsidies serve as seed capital, reducing financial barriers and enabling the development of innovative projects, particularly where costly technologies pose constraints. These are non-repayable funds, usually provided by governments, institutions, or NGOs to incentivize the adoption of sustainable practices. They tend to serve as seed capital that encourage the initiation and development of projects by reducing financial barriers. By alleviating upfront costs, grants and subsidies enable the development of innovative projects, particularly in the cases where costly technologies may pose constraints.

iv. Guarantees and risk-sharing mechanisms. These instruments aim to mitigate perceived risks associated with innovative ventures. They provide assurance and act as insurance against potential losses or default risks, encouraging private investors and financial institutions to provide capital for sustainable initiatives. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) are a common form of risk-sharing, reducing budgetary constraints by sharing risks, responsibilities, and rewards. PPPs leverage resources, expertise, and capital from both sectors, offering sustainable, long-term financing mechanisms for water circular economy initiatives. In the water sector, PPPs range from

partnerships between small enterprises and local governments to collaborations involving large supranational institutions and private firms.

v. Alternative funding. This category includes non-traditional financing mechanisms increasingly used for sustainability and circular economy projects. Crowdfunding involves collective financing by a large number of people through online platforms. Social impact bonds (SIBs) provide upfront capital for social projects, with investors receiving a return only if predetermined social outcomes are achieved. Lease financing allows organisations to fund asset acquisition without upfront payment, with leasing companies purchasing assets and renting them to lessees over a specified period. Lease financing is beneficial for expensive water infrastructure equipment or facility upgrades.

3. Circular economy of water

In line with the scarce amount of freshwater resources available on the Earth's surface and their overexploitation in recent decades and its forecast of being increased coupled with forecasts indicating further escalation -as per the World Water Development Report 2023, urban water demand is anticipated to surge by 80 per cent by 2050- to ensure equitable access to high-quality water, improved management of the entire water cycle is required.

Taking this into consideration, it is clear that we need to change our mindset, moving away from the basic provision of fresh water and focusing on how to reduce its consumption or improve its management in order to minimise water losses. It is really about keeping water circulating in the hydrological cycle for longer periods. This approach perfectly aligns with the principles of the circular economy. To prolong water circulation and appreciate its value, it is crucial to implement strategies focused on rethinking, reducing, and reusing.

Recent literature has explored various approaches to defining the role of water within the circular economy, each offering a unique perspective. Although these approaches share a common goal, none has yet become a standardised definition. The forthcoming discussion will cover these different perspectives, highlighting the significance of water in the circular economy.

- According to Morsetto et al. (2022), the circular economy of water is an economic framework aimed at reducing, preserving, and optimising water usage. This is achieved through waste avoidance, efficient utilisation, and quality retention, while also ensuring environmental protection and conservation.
- Salminen et al. (2022) define the water-smart circular economy (smart-water CE) as an economic concept whereby water is abstracted from the environment to the technosphere within the ecological boundaries of surface and groundwater bodies. In a water-smart CE, abstracted water is used efficiently to avoid losses. Energy absorbed by and substances mixed or dissolved in water during use are recovered for reuse, enabling the recycling of water for various purposes within the technosphere. A water-smart CE implies the use of secondary materials and the production of energy in a manner that minimises significant risks to water-related ecosystems and human health.
- The World Bank, as highlighted by Delgado et al. (2022), places greater emphasis on rethinking urban water, particularly through resilience lenses. The Water in Circular Economy and Resilience (WICER) Framework focuses on three main outcomes: delivering resilient and inclusive services, designing out waste and pollution, and preserving and regenerating natural systems. Ultimately, these efforts aim to improve livelihoods while valuing water resources and the environment.

There are various strategies and approaches being explored to implement principles of circular economy in water management, aiming to address the imbalance between forecasted demand and available supply. Among the proposed strategies is the active reuse of water, reducing consumption through efficient practices, and rejuvenating existing water bodies to optimise their supply capacity. Additionally, there are identified eight key value retention processes, such as refuse, reduce, reuse,

repair, among others, along with the guiding principle of reduce by design, guiding towards a more sustainable and efficient use of the water resource.

Experts in the field suggest a series of strategies categorised into three main areas: minimisation, optimisation, and retention of water use. These strategies range from measures to avoid unnecessary water usage to advanced treatment techniques allowing for the recovery of useful compounds or energy generation from wastewater.

Furthermore, a comprehensive framework based on key principles, such as sustainable water resource management, loss prevention, and harmful substance elimination from wastewater, is proposed. This framework provides guidance for designing water management systems that are both efficient and environmentally friendly.

The World Bank promotes the WICER Framework, which focuses on three fundamental aspects: delivering resilient and inclusive services, designing without waste or pollution, and preserving and regenerating aquatic ecosystems. This holistic approach aims to transform the way water is managed in urban environments, promoting circularity and resilience in water infrastructure (World Bank, 2021).

Figure 8. Water in Circular Economy and Resilience (WICER) (Source: World Bank, 2021)

Together, these strategies and frameworks offer a comprehensive approach to tackling current challenges in water management, encouraging sustainable and adaptive practices in this vital resource.

Transitioning to a fully circular water economy is a prolonged process with various drivers, incentives, challenges, barriers, and policy instruments influencing its pace. Financial benefits, including reduced costs and extended availability of public financing, are key drivers for organisations to embrace circular water solutions. However, barriers such as unclear regulations, negative attitudes, and technological limitations hinder progress.

4. Financing circular economy in the water sector

This section explores the financial instruments essential to fund the development and deployment of CE projects and innovations in the water sector. Given the capital-intensive and innovative nature of these projects, suitable financing mechanisms are crucial for addressing the unique risks and challenges associated with CE initiatives. Therefore, the section highlights those instruments that provide targeted support for CE projects, such as green bonds, public grants, public-private partnerships, and risk-sharing mechanisms. These instruments play a key role in not only securing the necessary funding but also in facilitating sustainable growth and innovation in water management. Here, the emphasis is on evaluating how effectively these tools address the specific financial needs of CE projects, and whether they sufficiently enable innovation and scaling in the sector.

4.1. Overview of financing the CE of water in Europe

Financing for circular economy projects in the water sector can be broadly classified into two sectors: public and private. Public financing aims to achieve welfare objectives, while private investment is driven by profit margins, with different levels of social and environmental responsibility. Understanding the available sources of financing in both sectors is crucial for project managers in initiating and scaling pilots. This section provides an overview of public and private financing sources, preceding an EU regulatory context.

4.1.1 Current financing landscape in Europe

Current and traditional water-based business models are financed according to the 3Ts concept developed by the OECD Horizontal Water Programme (Machete & Marques, 2021). This concept categorises the three primary financial sources for water sector investments: Taxes, Tariffs, and Transfers (mainly official development assistance) (Figure 13).

Figure 9. The 3T finance model in water sector (Source: Machete & Marques, 2021)

The innovative technologies implemented through the B-WaterSmart project represent significant advancements in water management efficiency. These improvements have positive environmental impacts, including the reduction of environmental footprints and the potential to repurpose valuable resources as inputs for new processes. This fosters the creation of new circular business models, enhancing the sector's marketability and enabling self-financing through potential new revenue streams.

While theoretically promising, the creation and development of new sustainable business models are complex in practice. As previously mentioned, financial barriers are a significant challenge in technological development and innovation. These advancements often involve high costs and require substantial initial investments, with no immediate profits. Furthermore, the regulated environments in which many of these technologies operate can lack economic incentives, making them less attractive to traditional private investors. Instead of simply uncertainty and high risk, the absence of clear economic benefits and incentives plays a critical role in deterring private financing (WATER-MINING, 2023). This highlights the essential role of the public sector in supporting the scalability of these projects, especially in their early stages when technologies are not yet fully matured (low TRLs) and have not yet been validated in environments similar to real-world conditions (TRL 6).

Figure 10. Technology Readiness Levels (TRL 1-TRL 9) (Source: The European Space Agency, 2020)

In today's landscape, there is a noticeable trend towards allocating funds to bolster sustainability, particularly in critical and vulnerable sectors like water. Yet, tapping into these financial reservoirs necessitates adherence to established taxonomies. It is imperative to discern the environmental and social merits of projects, ensuring they align with frameworks such as the European taxonomy. This

alignment facilitates access to a spectrum of financial resources, including ESG bonds, European funds, and more.

The European Union Taxonomy for sustainable activities is a comprehensive framework that classifies economic activities based on their environmental sustainability. This standardised classificatory system ensures the identification of which economic activities can be considered sustainable, contributing to at least one of the six environmental objectives defined. They must comply with the criteria of “do no significant harm” to any of the other five objectives and comply with essential social safeguards (TSUI, 2023).

The primary aim of this framework is to establish a cohesive inventory of environmentally viable undertakings within Europe. It seeks to prevent companies from making misleading claims about their environmental impact, known as greenwashing, and to establish a foundation for sustainability norms, tools, and standards (TSUI, 2023).

Figure 11. The EU Taxonomy. Environmental objectives (Source: TSUI, 2023)

The EU taxonomy outlines six environmental objectives: (1) Climate change mitigation; (2) Climate change adaptation; (3) Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources; (4) Transition to a circular economy; (5) Pollution prevention and control; (6) Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems.

The EU Taxonomy is important for the financial sector and the circular economy in the EU, as it has the power to steer money towards the circular economy transition. This is particularly relevant for the private sector (section 4.1.2), as a growing number of sustainable finance instruments can be used to support circularity and include it as a non-financial criterion (UNECE, 2023).

4.1.1. Public Financing

In the European Union, public funds for environmental projects are well-developed. Several supranational institutions offer financial support for water management and circular economy projects through grants, debt, and risk-sharing mechanisms. Following are some key European financing programs. A broader list of available financial instruments from each institution has been included in the Annex I for reference.

European Investment Bank (EIB)

The [European Investment Bank](#) offers a comprehensive range of financial solutions and advisory services designed to support projects aligned with circular economy principles, including those focused on the water sector, both management and infrastructure, that demand substantial investment and risk mitigation. The Circularity Metrics Lab estimates that €3.4Bn of lending was made available by the EIB for CE economy projects over the period 2018-2022¹³.

Through direct and intermediated loans, equity and quasi-equity investments, and blended finance arrangements, the EIB offers flexible funding options that cater to CE projects. Direct financing is provided to large scale projects (over 25 million euros), and are usually directed to multi-componente investments, for example a loan with a circular focus for a municipality. By providing guarantees and risk-sharing mechanisms, the EIB also enhances private sector participation, reducing perceived risks and improving the creditworthiness of CE innovative projects.

Indirect financing is done for smaller projects, which are normally grouped through an intermediary partner. Such partners may include financial institutions or funds, which have adequate due diligence processes and monitoring systems in place to ensure the proper support of eligible projects. An example of indirect funding is the programme “Smart Cities, Climate Action & Circular Economy II” developed in partnership with the Belgian bank Belfius. The focus of this programme is to finance smart, circular and climate action investments in cities.

The specialised financial instruments for CE are detailed below:

- **European Fund for Strategic Investments (EFSI)**¹⁴. The EFSI is a key part of the EIB strategy for financing high-risk and innovative projects, particularly those that advance the circular economy. As part of the Investment Plan for Europe, EFSI mobilises private capital for projects that contribute to sustainable development, such as water management and resource recovery, by addressing funding gaps for projects that may not attract conventional financing due to their risk profile or innovative nature.

Through flexible instruments like guarantees, subordinated loans, and equity investments, EFSI supports projects that may not qualify for traditional financing due to their innovative scope or higher risk profile. To further support innovation, the EIB also employs **InnovFin**, that provides tailored financial products designed to stimulate research and innovation in Europe. By offering loans, guarantees, and equity-type financing, InnovFin plays a crucial role in de-risking pioneering technologies essential for CE projects. These instruments help

¹³Source: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/circularity/thematic-metrics/enabling/circular-economy-lending>

¹⁴ For more details, visit: https://www.eif.org/what_we_do/efsi/how_to_apply_for_EFSI_financing/index.htm

bridge the funding gap, particularly for resource-intensive sectors like water management, where substantial capital and long-term commitment are required to achieve sustainability goals.

An example of EFSI and InnovFin's impact is the **Ecocentral Granada Project**¹⁵ in Spain, which received funding to develop advanced wastewater treatment technologies for water reuse and resource recovery. Located in Granada, this project transforms wastewater into high-quality reclaimed water for agricultural irrigation and generates biogas as a byproduct, which is used to produce renewable energy.

- **European Circular Bioeconomy Fund (ECBF)**¹⁶. The ECBF is a dedicated financial instrument aimed at supporting innovative CE projects, with a particular focus on bio-based industries. With a target size of €250 million, ECBF invests in pioneering projects within areas such as enabling technologies, biomass production, and bio-based materials, all of which contribute to a more sustainable, circular economy. The fund is managed in collaboration with the EIB's Innovation Finance Advisory and is designed to attract both public and private investments, thereby leveraging additional capital for high-impact projects.

ECBF provides flexible financing solutions that cater to companies at various stages of development, particularly those in early growth phases that require patient capital. This fund not only offers direct equity investments but also considers projects that need supplemental grant support, especially when innovative technologies are involved. By focusing on high-risk, high-reward initiatives, ECBF plays a crucial role in advancing Europe's bioeconomy and promoting sustainable, circular practices across a range of sectors.

An example of ECBF's impact is its investment in **Ecospray Technologies**, an Italian company specialised in environmental and bioenergy solutions. Ecospray developed an innovative wastewater treatment process that recovers valuable nutrients from wastewater, which can then be reused as fertilisers.

- **Grant recommendations:** For CE projects that may not be fully financially viable through traditional financing alone, the EIB offers grant recommendations as part of its blended financing approach. By identifying and recommending grants from EU programs, such as Horizon Europe and the LIFE Programme, the EIB helps projects access additional funding to cover costs that might otherwise be prohibitive. This blended financing model combines grant support with other financing tools, like loans or equity, to bridge funding gaps and enhance the project's overall financial sustainability.

An example of this approach is the **Aquafin Water Reuse Project** in Belgium, where the EIB recommended grants from the LIFE Programme to complement its loan. This project focuses on the recovery and reuse of treated wastewater for agricultural irrigation, contributing to sustainable water management and reduced freshwater dependency.

A recent assessment from the Circularity Metrics Lab, states that lending increased over the period 2016-2020 compared to the period 2014-2018, from EUR 2.4 to 2.7 billion. The sub-sectors Industry

¹⁵For more details, visit: https://www.resurgranada.es/cma_loma_manzanares.php

¹⁶ For more details, visit: <https://www.ecbf.vc/>

and services and Waste management have seen their relative share increase, while it has decreased for Water management¹⁷. Overall, the increase in total lending for CE is a positive trend. This trend is expected to continue in the next few years; as stated in its Climate Bank Roadmap, the EIB intends to reinforce its activities on the circular economy, including through financial support to circular economy projects¹⁸. Details on the application process and eligibility criteria can be found in Annex I.

Horizon Europe

[Horizon Europe - European Commission](#) is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation, with an indicative budget of €93.5 billion for 2021-2027 following the Multiannual Financial Framework Midterm Review (MTR) decision. The programme addresses climate change, advances the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, and enhances the EU's competitiveness and growth. It fosters collaboration, strengthens the impact of research and innovation, and supports the creation and dissemination of excellent knowledge and technologies. Horizon Europe creates jobs, fully engages the EU's talent pool, promotes industrial competitiveness, and optimises investment impact within a strengthened European Research Area. Legal entities from the EU and associated countries can participate, facilitating the development, support, and implementation of EU policies while tackling global challenges. This includes CE projects, such as water resource management, wastewater treatment, and sustainable water infrastructure, primarily under Pillar II, particularly Cluster 6, which focuses on activities ranging from basic research to demonstration projects. Only for the calls released during 2024, the budget for CE projects was €147.5 million. There were 16 related topics, such as increasing the circularity in electronics, plastics and textiles value chains; Innovative circular solutions for furniture, among others.

Europe Innovation Council (EIC)

The [EIC Fund - European Commission](#) is the venture arm of the European Innovation Council, established with a budget exceeding €10 billion to support deep tech innovators. It focuses on funding startups, SMEs, and mid-caps with high potential for market disruption. The Fund bridges the funding gap for high-risk, market-creating technologies by providing patient capital, thus attracting additional investors. By investing in early-stage, transformative technologies, the EIC Fund aims to foster innovation, boost industrial competitiveness, and generate a pipeline of potential unicorns. The Fund supports companies throughout their lifecycle, from early research to commercialization, and collaborates with the European Commission and the European Investment Bank. It plays a crucial role in scaling up breakthrough innovations in Europe while creating jobs and promoting economic growth.

The Joint Initiative on Circular Economy (JICE)

The [JICE](#), launched in 2019, aims to provide long-term financing for projects that accelerate the transition to a CE. The participating JICE partners are the EU's largest public promotional banks and institutions - Bank Gospodarstwa Krajowego (BGK - Poland), Caisse des Dépôts Groupe (CDC - France), including Bpifrance, the French investment bank, Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP - Italy), Instituto de Crédito Oficial (ICO - Spain) and Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW - Germany) – and

¹⁷ Source: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/circularity/thematic-metrics/enabling/circular-economy-lending?activeTab=091f27b0-d831-4060-a87f-c85adc2cd6ad>

¹⁸Source: https://www.eib.org/attachments/thematic/eib_group_climate_bank_roadmap_en.pdf

the European Investment Bank (EIB). Together, they have set a financing target of at least €10 billion for CE projects by the end of 2023. As of the end of 2022, projects worth €8.9 billion have been funded across a wide range of sectors, including agriculture, industry and services, mobility, urban development, waste and water management. Projects span all stages of the value chain and the life cycle of products and services, from design to value recovery.

In July 2023, the JICE decided to prolong the initiative beyond the original time frame (2023). At the same time, the partners decided to open their initiative to further interested and committed European public promotional banks and institutions.

For a wide range of CE projects, the participating institutions provide loans, equity investments, guarantees and technical assistance. They also develop innovative financing structures for public and private infrastructures, municipalities, private companies of different sizes, and research and innovation projects. In addition, the 5+1 Group, in liaison with the JICE work, contributes to ongoing European Commission initiatives by building knowledge and developing financing models through dedicated working groups. In this sense, JICE is increasingly participating in circular economy knowledge dissemination activities that will contribute to the development and diffusion of a circular economy culture in the European business and financial landscape.

LIFE Programme

The [LIFE - European Commission](#) is the EU's funding instrument for the environment and climate action. It focuses on several key areas, aiming to support projects that contribute to the transition towards a sustainable, circular, and resilient economy. LIFE has been supporting CE-related projects since 1992 through some 700 projects on waste prevention and reduction, recycling and reuse, totalling more than €1 billion of investment. Under the 2014 – 2020 LIFE programming period, more than €948 million was invested in over 215 projects that contributed to the circular economy. These projects also built on the CIP eco-innovation programme that helped innovative green ideas to become marketable solutions. LIFE CE projects have helped implement EU environmental legislation. And some have been pivotal for crafting and reviewing existing legislation. Several projects have increased citizens' awareness of waste prevention or established new processes for preventing waste. Others have contributed to 'closing the loop' upstream in such areas as product design, new production processes, consumer awareness and new value chains, as well as helping to protect our environment, these projects can lead to market solutions and new green jobs.

European Regional Development Fund (ERDF)

The [ERDF](#) is a key financial instrument within the European Union, dedicated to promoting economic, social, and territorial cohesion by addressing regional disparities. The fund's primary objective is to support investments that foster a smarter, greener, more connected, and inclusive Europe, thereby contributing to sustainable and balanced development across all member states. By focusing on reducing disparities between more developed and less developed regions, the ERDF enhances the EU's overall competitiveness and ensures that economic progress benefits all communities, bringing them closer to the EU's strategic objectives for regional development and social equity.

In alignment with the EU's commitment to a circular economy, the ERDF plays a critical role in financing projects that support sustainable resource management and environmental protection. The fund encourages investments in circular economy initiatives, such as waste reduction, recycling, sustainable water management, and renewable energy solutions. By supporting these projects, the ERDF helps regions transition from linear to circular models of production and consumption, which in turn promotes resource efficiency, reduces environmental impact, and drives long-term economic resilience. This approach not only contributes to the EU's Green Deal goals but also ensures that local communities can actively participate in and benefit from the shift towards a circular economy.

Innovation Fund (IF)

The [Innovation Fund](#) is one of the world's largest funding programs aimed at accelerating the development and deployment of innovative low-carbon technologies. Financed through revenues from the EU Emissions Trading System, the fund has an impressive budget of €40 billion for the decade spanning 2020 to 2030. Its primary focus is on supporting projects that can drive significant reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, thereby contributing to the EU's ambitious climate neutrality goals and reinforcing its leadership in global climate action.

The fund targets a wide range of sectors, including energy-intensive industries, renewable energy, energy storage, and carbon capture and storage. By supporting breakthrough technologies that address climate change, the Innovation Fund promotes the transition towards a circular and low-carbon economy. It provides substantial financial backing for projects that are too risky for private investors, ensuring that innovative solutions can be tested, scaled, and commercialised. This is especially valuable for circular economy projects, where innovative approaches are required to reduce waste, lower emissions, and optimise resource use across various industries.

One example of the Innovation Fund's impact is the **Kronospan Biomass Power Project** in Poland, which received funding to develop a biomass energy plant that uses wood waste as fuel. By converting industrial wood waste into renewable energy, this project reduces landfill waste and greenhouse gas emissions, embodying circular economy principles. The project not only supports Poland's energy transition but also aligns with the EU's objectives of reducing emissions and fostering sustainable resource management.

Key indicator of Public Finance in the EU

The following metrics, extracted from the Circularity Metrics Lab from the European Environmental Agency¹⁹ highlight the impact of the different efforts at the EU level made to foster CE. Based on multiple sources and data, they offer a valuable insight in the trend of CE implementation. They are classified in four parts, to allow a better understanding of the impact in different economic aspects:

Enabling Factors:

National CE Policies: 20 EU member states have published national circular economy policy documents by September 2022. These plans guide national efforts towards the development of a circular economy.

¹⁹Source: <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/circularity>

CE financing: €3.4Bn of lending was made available by the European Investment Bank for circular economy projects over the period 2018-2022. Targeted financing is a key measure to steer economic development towards more sustainable production and consumption patterns.

Scientific articles on CE: 3033 articles were published in scientific journals concerning circular economy innovations in the EU27 during 2021. This increased activity suggests there is a growing level of innovation in this area.

Business:

Circularity in Green public procurement: 26% of Belgian public procurement included some considerations for sustainability. Public authorities offer a high potential for driving the circularity transition through government purchasing power.

Circular business ranking and performance: 194 European companies have completed a Circulytics circularity assessment.

Certifications to European ecolabel: 398% increase was recorded in European ecolabel product certifications between 2010 and 2021. Paints and varnishes are the products with the highest number of ecolabels.

Eco-innovation scoreboard outcomes: 21% increase is reported for positive outcomes on the eco-innovation scoreboard across in the EU, with an increasing trend observed for most Member States. The Eco-Innovation Index measures the environmental innovation performance of EU Member States, on the basis of the 12 indicators included in the measurement framework.

Consumers:

Consumption footprint: 8.4 % decrease in Europe's consumption footprint between 2012 and 2020, although levels continue to exceed planetary boundaries. The EU must achieve a sustained reduction in the overall level of consumption while increasing the use of products that have less impact on the climate and environment.

Materials and waste

Circular material use rate: 11.7% of EU material use is supplied by recycling waste materials.

Waste recycling: 46% of overall waste in the EU is recycled.

Renewable energy: 21.8% of EU energy consumption is met from renewable sources

Europe's material footprint: 6.1Bn tonnes of materials are extracted from nature to provide the goods and services consumed by EU citizens. From 2010 to 2020, it remained relatively stable. In 2020 the material footprint fell by 5%, but is heavily influenced by the economic slowdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic,

Resource productivity: 2.1€/kg worth of production activity is generated for every kilogramme of material consumed in the EU economy.

Employment in the circular economy: 4.3 million people in the EU are working on CE. Political and economic momentum for the circular economy is building-up in Europe, including growth in financing for circularity projects. The introduction of circular economy strategies at national level is well-advanced across the EU.

European companies are displaying signs of adopting circular approaches in their business models, as evidenced by a strong growth in registrations to the European Ecolabel. Circular Economy is a significant reason for increases in employment in the EU with more than 4 million people employed in circular economy sectors in 2021.

The report points out that the EU's total material footprint is above the global average and much above those of low- and middle-income countries. This level of resource consumption exceeds the planet's 'safe operating space' for resource extraction, meaning that, if the world were to consume resources at the level of the EU, the capacity of the planet to provide these resources would be exceeded.

4.1.2. Private Financing

Overview of sustainable private financing

Sustainable private investment has grown rapidly in recent years. In 2021, the value managed by the sustainable finance industry exceeded €3.7 trillion. Capital markets have become dominant in advanced economies like Europe, with banks structuring financial products and selling them in capital markets to institutional investors (Environmental Finance - Sustainable Bonds Insight, 2023).

Sustainable investment funds integrate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria with traditional investment objectives such as profitability, safety, and liquidity. This approach seeks to ensure that investments not only achieve financial goals but also contribute positively to sustainability. By investing in sustainable funds, investors can align their financial aspirations with their values, supporting companies and projects that prioritise ESG considerations.

On December 14, 2023, the European Securities and Markets Authority (ESMA) issued [guidelines for using ESG-related terms in fund names](#). These guidelines aim to protect investors from misleading claims by requiring that at least 80% of a fund's investments meet specific ESG objectives. The guidelines also set criteria based on Paris-aligned and Climate Transition Benchmarks for using certain terms (ESMA - European Securities and Markets Authority, 2024).

Types of sustainable investment funds (klimaVest, 2024)

- *Sustainable Equity Funds*. Invest in shares of listed companies, impacting their ability to fund sustainable projects.
- *Green Bonds*. Finance sustainable projects, with ESG criteria applied in fund selection.
- *Sustainable Mixed Funds*: Combine various asset types, balancing risk, and return.
- *Sustainable Umbrella Funds*. Invest in multiple funds, diversifying risk but complicating sustainability tracking.
- *ESG Exchange-Traded Funds (ETFs)*. Select investments based on ESG criteria, either passively or actively, and may be more costly.
- *Sustainable Thematic Funds* concentrate on specific sustainability themes, such as renewable energy, water management, or waste reduction.
- *Impact Funds*. Emphasise transparency and measurable impact, directly investing in projects with tangible benefits.

Sustainable Equity Funds lead the market, representing over 60% of total assets, with passive strategies making up 27%. Despite facing challenges such as greenwashing and geopolitical instability, Europe continues to be a frontrunner in sustainable finance (Zeb Consulting, 2023).

In the water and waste management sector, mutual funds saw impressive growth, reaching nearly €36 billion in value in 2022 (Pudill, 2023). Notable examples include Fidelity's Sustainable Water & Waste Fund²⁰ and DWS ESG Blue Economy Fund²¹. These funds target investments in projects that tackle water and waste challenges, aiming to generate significant positive environmental impacts.

Figure 12. Sustainable bond volumes (Source: Sustainable Bonds Insight, 2023)

Steps for investing in sustainable funds

1. Define your objectives

²⁰ For more details, visit: https://www.fondosfidelity.es/fondos/ficha/L_U1892829828

²¹ For more details, visit: <https://funds.dws.com/es-es/fondos-de-renta-variable/lu2357944896-dws-concept-esg-blue-economy-nc/>

Determine if the focus is on financial returns, social or environmental impact, or both. Assess priorities in environmental sustainability, social equity, or governance, and consider your risk tolerance, as sustainable investments may vary in volatility.

2. Research funds

Review the performance of sustainable funds over 3, 5, or 10 years and compare them with traditional funds. Check ESG ratings to understand how well funds align with sustainable practices. Investigate the experience of fund managers and ensure that the fund's holdings match your values and goals.

3. Understand the Fund's approach

Learn how the fund integrates ESG factors into its investment decisions, whether it avoids certain industries or focuses on specific sectors. Decide between active management, where professionals make investment choices, or passive management, which tracks a sustainable index.

4. Monitor Performance

Regularly check how your funds are performing against your financial and impact goals. Adjust your portfolio as needed and stay updated on trends and changes in your fund's strategy or management.

5. Diversify investments

Spread investments across different asset types (stocks, bonds) to manage risk. Also, diversify across regions and sectors to reduce the impact of any single area underperforming.

6. Think long-term

Sustainable investing is often about playing the long game. Consider how global trends towards sustainability might affect the investments in the future. Be patient—sustainable funds might take a bit longer to show returns since they are usually focused on long-term outcomes.

7. Seek professional advice

If new to sustainable investing or uncertain about choices, consult a financial advisor specialising in ESG and sustainable investments. They can help tailor an investment strategy that aligns with your financial goals, risk tolerance, and values.

EU Green Bonds, a key component of sustainable finance

European green bonds are specialised financial instruments designed to support environmentally sustainable projects, now governed by a new regulation adopted by the Council of the European Union. This regulation establishes uniform requirements for bonds labelled as 'European green bonds' or 'EuGB,' ensuring alignment with the EU taxonomy for sustainable activities. These bonds play a crucial role in financing green technologies, energy and resource efficiency, and sustainable transport and research infrastructure. More than one-third of global green bonds are issued in euros.

Since their inception in 2007, the green bond market has experienced remarkable growth. In 2021, annual green bond issuance surpassed USD 500 billion for the first time, marking a 75% increase from 2020. Europe remains a leading player in this market, accounting for 51% of global green bond issuance in 2020. Despite this growth, green bonds still make up only about 3 to 3.5% of the total bond issuance market, indicating significant room for expansion. As investor and institutional interest in sustainability continues to rise, the green bond market is expected to grow substantially (European Parliament, 2023). More than one-third of green bonds issued worldwide are denominated in euros (Figure 11).

Figure 13. Global green bonds by currency (Source: European Council, 2023)

Figure 14. Green bonds issued by year, globally (Source: European Council, 2023)

Steps for issuing Green Bonds

1. *Understand Regulations and Standards*²². Familiarise yourself with the regulations governing green bonds in your region, such as the European Union's guidelines for 'European green bonds' or 'EuGB'. These regulations ensure that the bonds meet the EU taxonomy for sustainable activities and are used for financing environmentally sustainable projects.
2. *Develop a Green Bond Framework*. Create a clear and comprehensive framework outlining how the bond proceeds will be used for sustainable projects. This framework should include details on project selection, management of proceeds, and reporting. Ensure the framework aligns with industry standards and best practices.
3. *Obtain verification and certification*. Engage with an external reviewer or verifier to confirm that your green bond framework and the projects financed comply with green bond standards. This step may involve obtaining certification from recognized organisations such as the [Climate Bonds Initiative \(CBI\)](#) or a similar body.
4. *Prepare offering documents*. Draft detailed offering documents that outline the terms and conditions of the green bond issue, including the use of proceeds, environmental benefits, and reporting commitments. These documents are crucial for informing potential investors about the bond's sustainability impact and financial terms.
5. *Market the Green Bond*. Promote your green bond to potential investors, highlighting the environmental benefits and alignment with ESG criteria. Utilise investor presentations, roadshows, and marketing materials to communicate the value proposition and attract interest.
6. *Issue the Green Bond*²³. Coordinate with underwriters or financial institutions to execute the issuance of the green bonds. Ensure that the bond is listed on relevant exchanges or platforms to enhance visibility and liquidity.
7. *Report and communicate impact*. Provide regular reports on the use of proceeds and the environmental impact of the funded projects. Transparency in reporting is essential to maintaining investor confidence and demonstrating the bond's contribution to sustainability goals.

4.2. Financial structuring

Financial structuring is a crucial aspect of the project development phase, as it aims to create an investment opportunity that aligns with the objective of generating sustainable services for both beneficiaries and investors. This involves defining the risk-reward profile of the project, providing necessary insights for investors to make informed decisions, establishing roles and interests of each party, designing appropriate governance mechanisms, finance blend, and contractual structure, and framing the project's scope and features to mitigate risks and increase societal and financial returns (Ehrhardt et al., 2024).

²² For more information, visit:

https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/tools-and-standards/european-green-bond-standard-supporting-transition_en

²³ For a step-by-step guide, refer to the [Green Bond Handbook: A Step-By-Step Guide to Issuing a Green Bond](#)

When defining the financial structure of a project, it is important to differentiate between finance and funding. Finance refers to the capital provided to an organisation with the expectation of repayment, including an interest component. This type of funding is typically offered by financial institutions such as banks, or by investors like venture capitalists, business angels, and shareholders. Conversely, funding is money provided by companies or government sectors for a specific purpose. Unlike financing, funding is usually free of charge and does not require repayment. Funding is typically based on an agreement and is provided to support specific initiatives or projects (University of Plymouth, 2024).

In the water sector, funding traditionally comes from tariffs, transfers, and taxes (3T's). However, adopting circular economy principles in water management, as seen with projects like B-WaterSmart, can open up new revenue opportunities. By harnessing the economic potential of waste products and by-products, these initiatives can deliver substantial financial benefits. For example, processing wastewater sludge to extract valuable resources such as phosphorus, organic matter, and biogas not only mitigates environmental impacts but also produces sellable goods. These resources can be marketed or utilised across various industries, creating a fresh income stream. This approach not only diversifies funding sources but also improves the financial stability of water projects, making them more appealing to investors and enhancing the potential for returns that can repay investments.

4.2.1. Varying risk-return perspectives

Finance providers have different investment mandates that influence their risk tolerance, return expectations, and project preferences. Typically, higher risk levels are associated with the potential for higher returns. However, in non-market business models—where traditional economic returns may not be feasible—investors often seek value through alternative means (Beumer et al., 2022). Instead of relying on direct financial profits from the business model, they might look for benefits through supportive regulations, subsidies, or other incentives. In such cases, the focus shifts from immediate economic gains to long-term strategic advantages and compliance with favourable policies, which can help offset the lack of traditional financial returns and enhance the project's overall attractiveness.

Institutional investors, such as pension funds and insurance companies, tend to focus on large-scale projects that offer steady financial returns aligning with their long-term goals. Impact investors, such as business angels, may choose to finance smaller projects with the expectation of high short-term financial returns. Donors, on the other hand, may have a neutral stance towards risk but prioritise societal returns, such as sustainability, employment, or public health. Given that investment in innovative water infrastructure can also yield non-financial returns, there is an opportunity for financial structuring to align interests and blend different sources of financing.

Investors often face specific concerns when evaluating innovative projects in the water and sanitation sector. Governance issues, such as political interference in tariff setting and contract procurement, can diminish the sector's appeal. Furthermore, sustainable investments in circular economy projects might be viewed as riskier compared to traditional brownfield projects, primarily because they often depend on less established revenue streams. To address these concerns, proposals should clearly outline strategies for mitigating governance risks and demonstrate the viability of revenue streams. This might include showcasing successful case studies, securing

commitments from regulatory bodies, or developing diversified revenue models to offset the perceived risk. By addressing these factors and presenting robust, practical solutions, proposals can better capture investor interest and mitigate the opportunity cost of choosing innovative over traditional projects.

The project manager should carefully consider the appropriate financial blend that aligns with the current stage of the development cycle. Table 2 provides an overview of how different financial instruments fit each phase of the project cycle.

Table 2. Financial instruments and their alignment with project cycle phases

Source of finance	Project phase		
	Development	Construction	Operation
Public (social return objective)	Subsidy	Subsidy	Subsidy
	Grant	Guarantees and risk-sharing scheme	Viability gap funding
Private (financial return objective)	Equity	Equity	Equity
	Business Angels	Construction loan	Bonds
		Performance bonds	Senior debt
		Junior debt	Insurance
			Refinancing

Source: Own elaboration

5. Financing circular economy in Living Labs of B-WaterSmart

The B-WaterSmart project identifies and defines six Living Labs (LLs). These LLs have significant potential to evolve into new circular business models. However, these models are currently in a pilot stage, and within their strategy for scalability, a key barrier identified is the financial aspect. Transitioning to the described business models in D4.3 requires a financial strategy that identifies the best funding options to match the necessary investment.

For water infrastructure investment, long-term financing and stable, adequate revenue inflows are imperative. However, the funding of water projects varies across different countries within Europe due to their unique histories, management systems, and the complexity of water management needed to meet societal needs and government preferences. This section explores the specific local contexts of each studied case and examines how aligned the governments are with a mission-oriented strategy to create a financing ecosystem. Such an ecosystem would enable the development of water-based business models aimed at improving water management based on the principles of the circular economy.

Next, the identification of the specific environmental objectives of each LL studied in the B-WaterSmart project is explained. This will help determine which financial mechanisms were utilised for the implementation of the pilot phase and which can be accessed for scaling up, taking into account the local differences between regions. A series of interviews were conducted with each LL to assess their current and future financial mechanisms.

5.1. Alicante

5.1.1. Description of the case and identification of circularities

The Alicante LL is dedicated to the transformation of the existing wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) into biofactories, where waste is harnessed to produce energy, water, and industrial products for internal use within the plant or even for external users. This facility is municipally owned by Alicante.

The Rincón de León WWTP produces reclaimed water, which is complemented by a desalination plant that uses ultrafiltration membranes and reverse osmosis. This combined process yields water primarily used for agricultural and urban purposes, such as irrigation. However, the brine stream generated in the reverse osmosis is managed as waste and discharged into the sea, posing potential environmental risks. In the context of the B-WaterSmart project, the WWTP is implementing a pilot-scale treatment process using Selective Electrodialysis (SED) and electrochlorination (EC) to valorise the brine. SED separates ions, forming a dilute stream suitable for water reuse, while EC produces sodium hypochlorite (NaClO), a disinfectant widely used in water treatment. This treatment process aims to increase reclaimed water production by up to 100%. Additionally, a low thermal evaporation system (CEVAP) is being piloted to treat rejected water from sludge dewatering, recovering nutrients like ammonia for use as biofertilizer. Circular practices also involve a co-digestion process, combining sewage sludge with solid waste to produce biogas for energy cogeneration. The residual heat from this process supports the co-digestion cycle, with resulting digestate sludge utilised in cement production. The dry sludge resulting from this process is used in

cement production. Future opportunities include upgrading biogas to biomethane for local transport or grid injection. Lastly, a microturbine installed at the treated effluent line allows for energy recovery from the wastewater treatment process, further enhancing circularity.

Figure 15. Complete map of the circularities of LL Alicante (D4.3)

5.1.2. Circularity return

Currently, the energy generated by LL is used to meet the energy needs of the WWTP, with no immediate plans for further production expansion. Rincón de León is currently achieving 26-30% energy self-sufficiency, primarily through biogas (i.e., cogeneration) and, to a lesser extent, through solar panels. Notably, savings in sludge management also contribute to this efficiency.

5.1.3. Financing

The initial co-digestion pilot project, funded by B-WaterSmart (Horizon 2020), has advanced with the acceptance of the LIFE project (Life MERLIN) this year. Coordinated by Cetaqua, with Aguas de Alicante as a partner, LIFE MERLIN will start in September 2024. It will combine sludge pre-treatment with co-digestion to boost biogas production, aligning with RePowerEU's goals for energy independence and decarbonisation.

LIFE MERLIN will use saponification and ultrasound sonication to release enzymes from biomass, enhancing biogas production and improving sludge dewatering. A digital tool will also be developed to optimise co-digestion with locally available co-substrates.

This technology will be tested at the Murcia Este and Monte Orgegia (Alicante, Spain) WWTPs. If successful, it will be scaled up to other plants, increasing biogas production both nationally and across Europe.

5.1.4. Project scaling

The project's scaling strategy prioritises the production of biogas through a co-digestion process. This necessitates investment in industrial equipment to facilitate the reaction and a technological development to achieve the efficiency and production KPIs. Moreover, establishing commercial agreements for the procurement of industrial organic waste is crucial, as it serves as a fundamental input for expanding energy production. On the basis of document D4.4, the foreseen investment in fixed capital is €660,000, with estimated operating costs of €152,800 annually. This investment will be covered partially with the LIFE MERLIN Project.

The funding will be procured leveraging their public-private partnership model (Aguas de Alicante is participated 50% by the City council and 50% by Hidraqua). The water operator is willing to use their own financial resources to cover the remaining budget to scale up the project. The investment can be channelled through the sanitation tariff and the management of the industrial waste taken to the biogas facility.

The remaining three technologies addressed in Alicante's LL are still under assessment to define the scaling potential, with particular attention to the nutrient recovery (CEVAP) and the synergies with the cement industry. The microturbine and biomethane technologies need further development.

5.1.5. National approaches to circular financing

Alicante LL has the opportunity to carry out further investments in circular models using national funds - once the remaining technologies achieve a sufficient TRL. On the one hand, the PERTE²⁴ (Strategic Projects for Economic Recovery and Transformation) are a new public-private collaboration instrument involving various public administrations, companies, and research centres. Their goal is to drive major initiatives that significantly transform the Spanish economy. Among the twelve approved strategic projects, notable ones include the Circular Economy PERTE, the Water Cycle Digitalisation PERTE, the Renewable Energies, Renewable Hydrogen, and Storage PERTE, and the Industrial Decarbonisation PERTE. So far, over €38.6 billion from the Recovery Plan have been allocated to more than 674,000 recipients, achieving a resolution rate of 57.4% (España Digital 2026, 2024).

An additional source of funds is available since June 2024, as the Council of Ministers approved the conditions for the implementation of five facilities, financed with €40 billion in loans from the Recovery Plan, managed by the Official Credit Institute (ICO). These facilities will fund investment projects that promote the green and digital transition of companies, thereby enhancing their

²⁴ PERTE: Strategic Projects for Economic Recovery and Transformation. For more details, visit: <https://espanadigital.gob.es/en/measure/perte-strategic-projects-economic-recovery-and-transformation>

competitiveness (ICO, 2024). Specifically, the ICO will launch the ICO-Green Line²⁵, which will provide €22 billion to finance projects for businesses of all sizes and households, aiming to encourage the green transition. These loans can be used for projects related to sustainable transport, energy efficiency, renewable energies, industrial decarbonisation, water management, circular economy, and climate change adaptation. The financing is facilitated through four types of financial instruments: mediation lines with financial entities, direct ICO financing, purchase of debt securities, and venture capital investments. This financing line could be suitable for the scale up of the rest of circular strategies identified in Alicante LL.

5.2. Lisbon

5.2.1. Description of the case and identification of circularities

The water-smart challenge of the Lisbon LL derives from the dependency on distant freshwater resources which, under the existing climate change scenario, represents a risk for the growing population and economy. The green-blue infrastructure is a solution applied in Lisbon for tackling climate change impacts related to droughts, floods, and heat waves. As reclaimed water is a sustainable source, largely independent of climate uncertainty, it can contribute to reducing pressure on strategic freshwater resources and to allow resources' recovery, such as phosphorus. The Lisbon LL solutions and processes address this challenge by facilitating safe water reuse and increasing water-energy-phosphorus efficiency, improving Lisbon's climate readiness and resilience regarding water scarcity.

Lisbon's first circularity aims to use reclaimed water from urban WWTPs for urban green areas irrigation. The production of reclaimed water within the Lisbon LL pilot (AdTA's Beirolas resource recovery plant) is carried out through a sequence of treatment processes at the WWTP, through the following scheme: treated wastewater; sand filtration; microfiltration; and ultrafiltration. Next, the addition of chlorine to the reclaimed water provides a disinfection residual, a key barrier for water microbial stability as the reclaimed water travels in the distribution networks. This treatment scheme allows the production of reclaimed water with adequate quality for unrestricted urban irrigation (Class A, on a A to D scale, being A the best quality water, as established in the Portuguese Decree-Law 119/2019). Lisbon LL solutions – tools #17, #24, #25, and #27 address this circularity.

On the second hand, the reclaimed water production for industrial reuse is also being explored (Technology #1), with the development of a protocol for safe potable reuse in the beverage industry. The continuous 24/7 pilot plant for potable water reuse – an ozone and reverse osmosis plant further upgraded to include an activated carbon filter column – is being tested with different treatment schemes to compare different pretreatments of reverse osmosis towards operational performance and water quality.

²⁵ More information available at: <https://www.ico.es/en/prestamos-plan-recuperacion/ico-verde>

Figure 16. Complete map of the circularities of LL Lisbon (D4.3)

5.2.2. Circularity return

Currently, the Living Lab can produce 4,200 m³ of reclaimed water per day. However, to determine the return of circularity (RoC), detailed cost figures, including initial investment and operating costs, are required. The assumption is that these costs are covered by funding from the B-WaterSmart project and the municipality.

5.2.3. Financing

The pilot phase of this project, situated within the publicly owned WWTP, has been exclusively funded by the Lisbon Municipality and the B-WaterSmart project. Notably, no private capital has been involved thus far.

5.2.4. Project scaling

Scaling up the project presents several challenges, such as developing a reclaimed water distribution network and establishing quality monitoring systems. A crucial factor for future success is implementing a tariff model that accurately reflects production and distribution costs, which will require regulatory changes. Currently, no financing has been secured for scaling up the project. Cumulative investment in the water supply network over the period 2020-2030 has been estimated in document D4.4. The investment in fixed capital (CAPEX) is €30,966,758, covering the costs of

constructing pipelines, reservoirs, and pumping stations, as well as installing and replacing electromechanical equipment after 20 years of operation. Operating costs (OPEX) are estimated at €1,248,197.

As defined in the D4.4, the cost of the scale-up of the project could be recovered through a tariff for reclaimed water use or sanitation, which is still pending to be defined by the Water operator and the regulator. The anticipated water tariff could facilitate the acquisition of public and private financing.

5.2.5. National approaches to circular financing

The EIB has granted a €420 million loan to Águas de Portugal (AdP) to enhance water and sanitation infrastructure in Portugal, backed by the Juncker Plan. This loan will support over 1,000 projects nationwide, improving the quality and coverage of water services and wastewater treatment, benefiting over 8 million people, and creating more than 7,400 jobs. An additional €200 million in funding may be allocated to municipalities. This effort will help Portugal comply with European water sector legislation and promote the efficiency and sustainability of water resources.

The plan *Plano Estratégico de Abastecimento de Água e Gestão de Águas Residuais e Pluviais (PENSAARP) 2030*²⁶ anticipates a €5.5 billion investment in Portugal's water sector by 2030, with half allocated for infrastructure rehabilitation. The sector needs to maintain an average annual investment of €500 million, gradually shifting from new infrastructure to rehabilitating existing assets. The main funding source will be the Portugal 2030 Multiannual Financial Framework.

The plan includes over 20 interventions, such as renovating or constructing WWTPs in various locations. Prepared since 2020, it replaces PENSAARP 2020 and incorporates rainwater management. It outlines four strategic objectives: service efficiency, sustainability, and economic, environmental, and societal value. The plan features specific goals and 70 measures to strengthen the sector, addressing issues such as stagnant performance indicators, climate change challenges, water scarcity, and increased flood risks.

5.3. East Frisia

5.3.1. Description of the case and identification of circularities

The East Frisia LL is facing increasing water demands from industrial, agricultural, and residential sectors, a trend accelerated by climate change. To safeguard groundwater resources, it is crucial to use drinking water solely for essential purposes. Thus, sectors where drinking water can be replaced by water from alternative sources are identified. At the DMK dairy in Edewecht, the B-WaterSmart pilot plant is deployed to trial treating condensate of whey water (COW water) to produce water suitable for industrial use as a substitute for drinking water.

Currently, the dairy industry, represented by the DMK Group, partially reuses COW water, which is water separated from milk during processing, without further treatment for backwashing. Additionally,

²⁶ PENSAARP2030: <https://apambiente.pt/agua/pensaarp2030>

the vapour condensate from milk processing, also referred to as COW water, is being tested in the B-WaterSmart project to produce water suitable for industrial use. A pilot plant has been established to improve the treatment of COW water for reuse in the water-intensive dairy sector. This treatment combines biological processes, ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis, and ultraviolet disinfection to produce purified water suitable for reuse.

The circularity efforts of the East Frisia LL are including treating alternative water resources, such as municipal, industrial, or urban wastewater, to produce additional reclaimed water. This reclaimed water can then be repurposed for non-potable uses, particularly in industrial settings.

Figure 17. Complete map of the circularities of LL East Frisia (D4.3)

5.3.2. Circularity return

Currently, 350,000 m³ of COW water per year is used without any additional treatment. The focus of the circularity return is on the utilisation of approximately 600,000 m³ of additional COW water per year in the industrial process for non-potable uses.

In the pilot plant, the water is not used due to legislative restrictions, resulting in no circularity return in the current scenario. The capital expenditure (CAPEX) for this plant is €800,000.

Upon scaling up, approximately 600,000 m³ of COW water per year will be treated. From this amount, it is expected that between 70% and 80%, or 420,000 to 480,000 m³ per year, will be utilised. The CAPEX required for this expansion is €9,000,000.

The ratio of cubic metres regenerated per euro invested is estimated to be between 0.047 and 0.053 m³/€. The operating expenditure (OPEX), including personnel, energy consumption, and chemicals, is calculated at 0.50 €/m³.

5.3.3. Financing

The financing for the pilot plant in East Frisia, operated by DMK, is a combination of project funding and private sector investment from EnviroChemie, a company specialising in water and wastewater treatment solutions. According to document D4.4, the planned investment in fixed capital for the project is €5,000,000, with estimated operating costs of €133,000.

5.3.4. Project scaling

The existing legal framework poses challenges for effectively implementing circular water reuse. While the European Water Reuse Regulation focuses on alternative irrigation sources for agriculture and horticulture, it neglects other forms of water reuse, such as for human consumption or beverage production. Additionally, discrepancies between the Regulation's standards for "Class A" reclaimed water and those for drinking water create barriers to direct potable reuse.

Efforts to explore funding opportunities for scaling up water reuse technologies have been made at various levels. For instance, Lower Saxony's Environmental Ministry provides support through a fund for sustainable water management initiatives aimed at addressing climate change impacts. However, this grant is inadequate for significant upscaling projects, and eligibility is restricted to municipal companies and public institutions, excluding entities like DMK. The communal water supplier OOWV does meet the criteria for accessing the grant. Despite DMK's application to the federal environmental innovation programme (Umweltinnovationsprogramm), the lack of success diminishes the likelihood of securing similar grants soon. Moreover, no other substantial national funds are anticipated.

Germany's national water strategy sets ambitious goals for water management, yet uncertainties persist about funding and implementation, exacerbated by a noticeable decline in political prioritisation of water issues in favour of green hydrogen initiatives. This reduced focus on water management is reflected in limited funding availability. The interplay between green hydrogen development and water resources highlights the need to address freshwater pressures, which are crucial for expanding water-intensive industries. The absence of private capital involvement in these initiatives underscores the importance of evaluating this gap. Private investors are often deterred by the lack of immediate economic incentives and regulatory support, highlighting a significant challenge in financing water reuse projects.

5.3.5. National approaches to circular financing

In 2019, the German government launched the "Water Research and Innovation for Sustainability – Water" programme to advance sustainable water research and innovation. The programme targets three key areas: water reuse through municipal wastewater treatment, water recycling in industry, and treatment of saline groundwater and surface water. Eligibility for funding under the programme is open to private sector entities, NGOs, and government institutions at all levels, with non-repayable

grants covering up to 50% of eligible project costs for commercial enterprises and research institutions engaged in economic activities.

In Lower Saxony, €8.2 million in funding for water management initiatives addressing climate change-related challenges is distributed across three funding rounds. Currently, 34 projects have received funding in the first round.

5.4. Bodø

5.4.1. Description of the case and identification of circularities

The primary objective of LL Bodø is to explore various options for converting waste into energy at a waste management facility. The first alternative involves co-digesting sludge and organic waste (e.g., food waste and fish sludge) from Bodø and Salten cities in Norway to produce compost and biogas. This process entails implementing thermal hydrolysis followed by anaerobic digestion and composting, with the inclusion of garden waste in the composting phase. Similarly, the second alternative follows the same process but generates biopellets instead of compost through a pelletizing process.

In the third alternative, sludge, and organic waste from Bodø and Salten are co-digested to produce biosolids (treated digestate) and mixed with garden waste for biochar production. This process involves thermal hydrolysis, anaerobic digestion, and pyrolysis. The fourth pathway mirrors the third alternative but uses an Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (UASB) instead of anaerobic digestion for the liquid fraction from sludge and organic waste treatment. Biosolids and garden waste are also combined for biochar production.

The exploration of these alternatives aims to increase energy production through biogas, which can be utilised not only within the facility but also distributed to the public network for electricity and heat generation. Additionally, by-products such as compost and biopellets can be repurposed in the agriculture sector to enhance soil quality by providing nutrients or serving as soil conditioners.

Figure 18. Complete map of the circularities of LL Bodø (D4.3)

5.4.2. Circularity return

The central goal of the project is to transform the sludge, currently composted and disposed of in landfills, into a valuable resource reintegrated into the productive cycle. One potential approach under consideration is converting the sludge into biochar, which can serve as a renewable energy source. By repurposing waste into a marketable product, the project aims to enhance its circularity and environmental sustainability.

5.4.3. Financing

The project is primarily funded by the B-WaterSmart grant and the local municipality. As of now, no private capital has been involved in financing this initiative. The absence of private funding is largely due to the perceived high risk and uncertainty associated with innovative CE projects, especially in the early stages where returns are not immediate and the market for by-products like biochar is still developing. Additionally, the regulatory environment and the need for long-term, stable returns may not align with the investment mandates of traditional private investors. However, as the project progresses and demonstrates its viability and potential for generating consistent revenue streams, opportunities for attracting private capital could increase, particularly if supported by favourable regulations and public-private partnership models designed to mitigate risks.

5.4.4. Project scaling

Developers are actively exploring cost-effective methods for managing sludge with a focus on maximising circularity. Selection criteria for scaling up will consider the extent to which different solutions contribute to circularity, particularly in terms of raw material recovery. To ensure that a high enough quantity of sludge is obtained, it is essential to secure long-term contracts with neighbouring municipalities. Ultimately, the goal is to establish a self-sustaining model that ensures the project's long-term viability and impact.

Once the model is defined, financing channels can be found through national sources (next section) or private financial institutions. Giving the context and preceding funding sources, public financing seems the most feasible option for the Bodø LL.

5.4.5. National approaches to circular financing

At the climate summit in Glasgow (COP26) in November 2021, Norway pledged to double its climate finance for developing countries by 2026, increasing from NOK 7 billion in 2020 to NOK 14 billion. This commitment includes at least tripling the funding for climate change adaptation, aligning with the Paris Agreement's goal to balance financial resources between mitigation and adaptation.

The Norwegian government has already laid the groundwork for an expanded adaptation effort, and this strategy will provide the framework for implementing the increased funding for adaptation measures. In 2020, Norway's climate finance comprised NOK 6.6 billion in public funds and NOK 400 million in mobilised private capital.

Possible financing options include Enova, a governmental body that can be approached for funding and/or loans for large projects such as biogas and hydrogen. In 2024, Enova has a budget of over NOK 8.3 billion, which is 43% more than in 2023.

5.5. Flanders

5.5.1. Description of the case and identification of circularities

The Flanders Living Lab has set out to establish a regional framework for improving and monitoring water intelligence, which involves the effective collection, analysis, and use of water-related data. The primary focus is on promoting safe water reuse and enhancing the integration of natural water systems. The goal is to create models for water availability, demand, and potential alternative sources, while also demonstrating the practical application of water reuse (Figure 16). Various local initiatives involving alternative water sources are currently under investigation, including the exploration of alternative resources for drinking water production, further purification of surface water through reverse osmosis, and the collection and reuse of rain and stormwater for agricultural purposes.

To meet these objectives, stormwater from urban areas will be collected in a specially designed basin intended for flood prevention. This basin is engineered to facilitate efficient collection while maintaining flood prevention measures. The collected stormwater undergoes treatment using sand filtration before being repurposed for agricultural irrigation through subirrigation, thereby bolstering

the resilience of the groundwater system. Additionally, efforts are underway to enhance drinking water production resilience by upgrading treatment processes to accommodate irregular raw surface water quality and by incorporating the indirect use of municipal wastewater treatment plant effluent for drinking water production. This requires implementing pre-treatment and advanced membrane processes to enhance drinking water quality. It is important to note that the circularity of stormwater management is distinct from drinking water production processes.

The pilot project in Flanders is currently in the development stage under the guidance of Aquafin and is slated for eventual transfer to Pidpa, the local utility company, pending agreement on pricing terms.

Figure 19. Complete map of the circularities of LL Flanders (D4.3)

5.5.2. Circularity return

This initiative focuses on capturing stormwater and treating it for agricultural use, primarily to mitigate floods in the city of Mechelen. By repurposing stormwater for agricultural irrigation, the project demonstrates a commitment to circularity and environmental sustainability, saving other sources of water for drinking water, and avoiding additional investments to adapt the city to flooding events.

5.5.3. Financing

The City of Mechelen had already planned to construct a buffer basin to manage flooding risks caused by stormwater runoff from upstream suburban areas, funding the basic infrastructure costs. Additional adaptations, such as the weather-controlled valve, were financed through the B-WaterSmart project, which also supported the inclusion of the sub-irrigation component to the

buffer basin. While existing drainage systems were funded by farmers, the adaptation to a subirrigation system and the pilot container were also facilitated by B-WaterSmart financing. The project was realised through contributions from Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt, Aquafin, VITO, and Stad Mechelen, all enabled by the B-WaterSmart grant.

So far, no private capital has been involved in the project. The lack of private investment may be attributed to the project's early stage and the specific nature of its benefits, which are more aligned with public goods and community resilience than immediate financial returns. However, there has been interest from local businesses in supporting the project by donating annually to the buffer basin as part of their sustainability objectives. As the project demonstrates its value and potential for broader application, there may be increased opportunities to engage private investors, particularly those with an interest in corporate social responsibility (CSR) or sustainability-focused initiatives.

5.5.4. Project scaling

Scaling the project is twofold: rolling out the concept of stormwater use and replicating the Mechelen case. The first one is more important. By adapting new and existing buffering infrastructure, water can be saved and provided towards a variety of end users, depending on local needs. Because of the urban planning issues in Flanders, there are many opportunities to apply the concept. Copying the Mechelen case of subirrigation will be a case specific application within the expansion of the general concept. In every case, progressive thinking and clear agreements between different stakeholders are key to success. The Flemish government financed the project 'Restwater' in the Blue Deal program. Part of this project is focused on buffering and reuse of stormwater and thus replicating the Mechelen case. The findings from the Mechelen case are directly applied in the plans made for the 'Restwater' project, since Aquafin is involved in both.

5.5.5. National approaches to circular financing

Between 2019 and 2022, the Flemish Government invested around €120 million in circular innovation. Flanders is also further investing in research and monitoring of its own performance with the monitor and a new Circular Economy Policy Research Center for the period 2022-2026. The Blue Deal and Stormwater Management Plans required by municipalities in Flanders, provide other financial incentives for circular options in the region.

5.6. Venice

5.6.1. Description of the case and identification of circularities

The Venice Living Lab focuses on addressing environmental challenges posed by human activities and climate change. It implements resource recovery and circular economy strategies to enhance the region's delicate balance, addressing issues like water scarcity and underutilised resource valorization potential. Proposed solutions include treating wastewater to obtain reclaimed water and increasing industrial and agricultural water reuse. With B-WaterSmart solutions, WWTPs act as

biofactories, producing reclaimed water, recovering nutrients, and valorizing wastewater sludge for energy and fertiliser production.

The first circularity in the Venice Living Lab aims to produce reclaimed water for industrial water reuse through a series of technological treatments. This includes ultrafiltration, reverse osmosis, and electro-deionization to produce high-purity water. Testing is conducted to assess the suitability of the reclaimed water for various industrial needs. The PIF plant, located at the Fusina WWTP effluent, is involved in reclaiming water for non-potable reuse, although adjustments may be needed for industrial reuse. Nutrient recovery, the second circularity, focuses on recovering nitrogen and producing salts for agricultural applications. Various stripping technologies are compared to select the most effective and economical option. Co-digestion is also explored to increase nutrient recovery and biogas production. The third circularity explores sustainable treatment and disposal solutions for wastewater sludge, considering factors like energy generation, fertiliser production, and agricultural reuse, with a decision support system aiding in the evaluation of different valorization pathways.

Figure 20. Complete map of the circularities of LL Venice (D4.3)

5.6.2. Circularity return

The Venice project aims to achieve three distinct circularities: (1) converting wastewater into reclaimed water for use in agricultural and industrial activities, (2) transforming wastewater into raw resources like ammonium salt, and (3) revalorizing wastewater sludge. By implementing these

circular processes, the project seeks to minimise wastewater generation and maximise resource efficiency.

5.6.3. Financing

The pilot project, located at the publicly owned WWTP, has been entirely funded by the Veneto Municipality and the B-WaterSmart project. Notably, no private capital has been involved in funding this initiative so far. This lack of private investment can be attributed to the project's current focus on public goods, such as environmental sustainability and resource recovery, which are typically seen as less immediately profitable and more suited to public sector involvement.

Moreover, the regulatory complexity and the early stage of the technologies involved may deter private investors who prioritise quicker returns and lower-risk ventures. However, as the project progresses and demonstrates its economic viability—particularly through the sale of reclaimed water and recovered resources like ammonium salt—there may be opportunities to attract private investment. For instance, companies with strong corporate social responsibility (CSR) agendas or those interested in sustainable industrial practices might see value in supporting the project as it scales up and seeks to commercialise its outputs.

5.6.4. Project scaling

While the pilot project has made significant progress, scaling up presents several challenges. A major issue is clearly defining the client base for reclaimed water, particularly among industrial users in the Porto Marghera area. Additionally, efforts are being made to simplify the procedures for obtaining the necessary regulatory permits to sell recycled raw materials, such as ammonium salt. However, as of the interview, no financing has been secured for scaling up the project, underscoring the need for further support and investment to overcome these challenges and achieve its full potential.

Based on document D4.4, the expected investment in fixed capital (CAPEX) is €3,500,000, with estimated operating costs (OPEX) of €1,056,190. Due to the amount considered, Venice LL is more likely to find financing options from public sources, once the technological and regulatory barriers are overcome. In order to attract private investors it is also necessary to define further the revenue model, the industries able and willing to join the CE model - i.e. to demand the reclaimed water produced -, which will make the return of investment visible, in addition to the environmental and natural resources benefits.

5.6.5. National approaches to circular financing

The Ecobilancio, a government document detailing the environmental expenditure of central government administrations, reported €4.7 billion in environmental spending for 2020. The state government's Ecobilancio for 2021, categorised by environmental objectives and types of expenditure, planned for approximately €6 billion in environmental spending for 2021, €4.7 billion for 2022, and €4.9 billion for 2023. Three-quarters of this expenditure is capital expenditure (mainly transfers), with only €1.4 billion as current expenditure. About half of the €6 billion planned for 2021 was allocated to soil and water protection management (30%) and research and development (19%).

The air and climate category ranked third, accounting for less than 12% of the total planned expenditure.

At the national and regional levels, in addition to EU funding opportunities (Life, H2020, and ERDF programmes), utilities and other stakeholders in the water sector have access to additional funding and incentives for circular economy projects. The National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) has allocated €15.37 billion to Mission 2 Component 4 (M2C4), focusing on hydrogeological instability, biodiversity protection, and sustainable water resource management.

ARERA, the Italian Regulatory Authority for Energy, Networks, and the Environment, has introduced incentives to enhance resource efficiency through its MTI-3 tariff methodology, which governed tariffs from 2021 to 2023. This framework provided higher allocation factors for activities promoting energy and environmental sustainability. The updated MTI-4 tariff methodology continues this approach but adds new features, including incentives specifically for wastewater reuse. It utilises the Fund for the Promotion of Innovation (managed by the CSEA) to reward the reuse of treated wastewater and updates the coverage of electricity costs related to such initiatives. Additionally, MTI-4 introduces the M0-Water Resilience macro indicator to assess the effectiveness of climate change mitigation actions undertaken by utilities.

5.7 Financing Gap Analysis

This section aims to present an summarised assessment of the gaps on financial sustainability of the LLs projects presented above.

Alicante, Spain

- **Gap in private investment:** Despite promising technological advancements in wastewater treatment and reuse, the Alicante LL struggles to attract private investors due to perceived risks and regulatory uncertainties.
- **Funding for scaling infrastructure:** The current public funding covers pilot-scale projects but does not extend to scaling infrastructure needs, especially for the biogas production and co-digestion facilities critical for broader impact.
- **Limited national support:** National funding options are restrictive, with insufficient tailored support for CE projects involving innovative, high-risk technologies.

Lisbon, Portugal

- **Lack of Dedicated Tariff Model:** The absence of a tariff model that reflects the full costs of reclaimed water production deters investment and scalability of water reuse initiatives.
- **Gaps in Infrastructure Funding:** Significant investments are required for developing a reclaimed water distribution network, which current funding mechanisms do not adequately address.
- **Private Investment Barriers:** Like Alicante, Lisbon struggles to secure private capital, as private investors seek more stable, profitable projects over high-risk circular economy pilots.

East Frisia, Germany

- **Regulatory Restrictions:** Existing water reuse regulations prioritize agricultural applications but provide limited support for industrial reuse applications in the dairy sector, inhibiting scaling efforts.
- **Insufficient Private Capital:** The legal and economic uncertainties, combined with high costs, limit the appeal of private investment for scaling up water treatment solutions.
- **Limited National Grants for Private Entities:** Available national grants are accessible only to municipal bodies, creating a barrier for private-sector actors like DMK in accessing government-supported financing.

Bodø, Norway

- **High-Risk Perception:** Innovative technologies such as biochar production and biopellets from sludge treatment are perceived as high-risk, making it challenging to attract private investors in early stages.
- **Regulatory and Market Barriers:** Regulatory complexity, coupled with a nascent market for by-products like biochar, limits access to private capital and opportunities for scaling.
- **Limited Private Funding:** The project currently relies on public funds, as private investors hesitate due to long payback periods and uncertainty in revenue from emerging circular products.

Flanders, Belgium

- **Early-Stage Infrastructure Needs:** Investment in stormwater buffering and subirrigation infrastructure is high, with limited initial private-sector involvement due to the absence of immediate financial returns.
- **Scaling Constraints:** Expanding the Mechelen stormwater reuse project model regionally requires long-term investment that existing funding mechanisms do not cover.
- **Public-Private Coordination Barriers:** Despite interest from local businesses, a structured public-private framework for sustained investment has yet to be developed, limiting scalable impact.

Venice, Italy

- **Complex Regulatory Environment:** Stringent regulatory requirements for reclaimed water use, especially in industrial applications, hinder private investment in scaling circular water systems.
- **Commercialization Challenges for By-products:** Although reclaimed water and ammonium salts offer commercial potential, the lack of streamlined regulatory support for these sales restricts market entry.
- **Funding for High CAPEX Requirements:** The pilot-scale projects require substantial CAPEX to scale, with insufficient private-sector interest due to high initial costs and long return on investment timelines.

6. Conclusions

The analysis presented in this report highlights the considerable progress made in financing circular economy projects within the water sector, particularly in Europe. Through an examination of both public and private financing mechanisms, it becomes clear that the financial landscape is evolving rapidly to support sustainable water management practices aligned with circular economy principles.

Public financing institutions such as the European Investment Bank (EIB), Horizon Europe, Europe Innovation Council (EIC), LIFE program, European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), and Innovation Fund (IF) play a crucial role in providing financial support for circular economy projects in the water sector. These institutions offer a diverse range of financial instruments, including grants, loans, and support for innovative technologies, to promote environmentally sustainable water management practices. Key initiatives such as the EIB's investments in water infrastructure projects and the Horizon Europe program's focus on research and innovation underscore the European Union's commitment to advancing circular economy principles in the water sector.

However, it is important to note that none of the Living Labs (LLs) examined in this report have yet secured private capital financing, which reflects a broader challenge in attracting private investment to innovative but high-risk and often non-profitable projects in this sector. This situation is not coincidental and highlights the significant opportunity cost that private investors face when choosing between circular economy projects in the water sector and more immediately profitable investments.

The growing sustainable finance industry, characterised by sustainable investment funds and green bonds, presents promising opportunities for private investment in circular economy projects within the water sector. Nevertheless, the reality remains that private capital is often reluctant to invest in projects that do not offer quick returns or are situated within regulated environments with limited economic incentives. To address this, mechanisms like the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities, which categorises and defines sustainable economic activities, and the expansion of green financial products, are crucial. These frameworks help in aligning private investments with long-term sustainability goals and mitigating some of the perceived risks associated with circular economy projects.

Effective financial structuring is essential for unlocking the full potential of circular economy projects in the water sector. By aligning investment opportunities with sustainable service delivery and societal goals, project developers can attract a diverse range of financing sources and mitigate risks for investors. However, in cases where projects are not economically profitable, it is clear that public funding will need to play a dominant role. This underscores the need for these projects to justify their benefits, not just economically, but also in terms of their social and environmental impacts. This justification is essential for maintaining public support and ensuring that such projects continue to receive the necessary funding.

Understanding the unique local contexts of water management across different regions in Europe is crucial for designing tailored financing strategies that address specific barriers and challenges to scaling up circular business models. Initiatives such as the B-WaterSmart project exemplify the importance of leveraging local partnerships and innovative financing mechanisms to overcome financial obstacles and drive meaningful impact in the water sector. Yet, to fully scale these projects and attract private investment, there must be a continued effort to improve the economic viability of

these projects, possibly through regulatory support, subsidies, or the creation of new markets for the by-products of circular water management processes.

Advancing circular economy principles in the water sector requires a concerted effort from both public and private stakeholders to mobilise financial resources, foster innovation, and promote sustainable development. By leveraging the diverse array of financing instruments available, embracing innovative financial structuring approaches, and adhering to sustainability frameworks, the water sector can transition towards a more resilient, resource-efficient, and environmentally sustainable future. Collaborative partnerships, strategic investments, and a shared commitment to circular economy principles will be essential in realising this vision and ensuring the long-term sustainability of water resources for generations to come.

Ultimately, the path forward involves not only securing public and private financing but also ensuring that the benefits of these projects—whether social, environmental, or economic—are clearly demonstrated and communicated. This will be key to overcoming the barriers to private investment and ensuring that circular economy projects in the water sector can be successfully scaled and replicated.

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Annex I - General Financial Instruments: description, eligibility and application process

European Investment Bank Financial instruments:

- **Loan**²⁷. The EIB provides medium and long-term loans with either fixed or variable interest rates. These loans are aimed at large-scale projects such as wastewater treatment and circular water management. For smaller projects, financing is available indirectly through local banks and intermediaries, particularly benefiting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The EIB typically covers up to 50% of a project's total cost, with loans starting at €25 million and terms extending up to 30 years.
- **Equity financing**²⁸. The EIB invests or co-invests in projects, especially those within infrastructure, environmental sectors, or SMEs. This investment helps attract additional funding from other investors.
- **Guarantees**²⁹. The EIB provides guarantees to mitigate risks associated with both large and small projects. This includes offering loan portfolios to enhance the attractiveness of projects to potential investors.
- **Blended finance**³⁰. EIB financing can be combined with other investment sources, such as EU grants and additional financial instruments, to address financing gaps and share risks.

1. Advisory services:

- **Expert guidance**³¹. The EIB offers technical and financial advice to assist in project development and implementation, as well as to improve institutional and regulatory frameworks.

2. Specialised financial instruments:

- **European fund for strategic investments (EFSI)**³². For projects involving higher risks or innovative approaches, the EIB utilises EFSI, InnovFin, and other specialised instruments designed to support these ventures.
- **European Circular Bioeconomy Fund (ECBF)**³³. With a targeted size of €250 million, the ECBF supports innovative circular economy projects in areas such as enabling technologies, biomass production, and bio-based materials. Managed by the EIB's Innovation Finance Advisory, this fund also considers projects needing additional grant support.

3. Additional support:

²⁷ For more details, visit: <https://www.eib.org/en/products/loans/index.htm>

²⁸ For more details, visit: <https://www.eib.org/en/products/equity/index.htm>

²⁹ For more details, visit: <https://www.eib.org/en/products/guarantees/index.htm>

³⁰ For more details, visit:

<https://www.eib.org/en/products/mandates-partnerships/eu-blending-facilities/index#:~:text=Blending%20involves%20the%20strategic%20use,p,projects%20and%20making%20them%20bankable>

³¹ For more details, visit: <https://www.eib.org/en/products/advisory-services/index.htm>

³² For more details, visit: https://www.eif.org/what_we_do/efsi/how_to_apply_for_EFSI_financing/index.htm

³³ For more details, visit: <https://www.ecbf.vc/>

- **Grant recommendations:** For projects that may not be fully financially viable, the EIB can recommend potential sources of grants to complement the financing.

How to get started?

i) Review financial products. Interested parties should visit the EIB website ([European Investment Bank](#)) to explore available financial products and identify options that best fit their project's needs.

ii) Contact advisory services. Engaging with the EIB's advisory team can provide valuable assistance in project planning, financial structuring, and regulatory compliance.

By leveraging these financial products and services, stakeholders can secure the support necessary to advance their water-related and circular economy projects, both within Europe and globally.

Additional Information. There is a [Frequently Asked Questions](#) section in their website for further information.

Horizon Europe funding schemes

1. Types of actions and funding schemes

- Research & Innovation Actions (RIA)³⁴
 - EU Funding Rate: 100%
 - Scope: establishing new knowledge or exploring the viability of new/improved technologies, products, processes, services, or solutions.
 - Activities: basic and applied research, technology development, integration, testing, and validation of small-scale prototypes.
 - RIA Lump Sum Actions: funding provided as lump sums for awarded grants.
- Innovation Actions (IA)³⁵
 - EU Funding Rate: 100% for non-profits, 70% for others
 - Scope: producing plans, designs, prototyping, testing, demonstrating, piloting, large-scale product validation, and market replication.
 - IA Lump Sum Actions: funding provided as lump sums for awarded grants.
- Coordination & Support Actions (CSA)
 - Scope: measures like standardisation, dissemination, awareness-raising, networking, policy dialogues, and studies.
 - CSA Lump Sum Actions: funding provided as lump sums for awarded grants.

³⁴ More information available at: https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_ECSEL-2017-2

³⁵ More information available at: https://cordis.europa.eu/programme/id/H2020_ECSEL-2017-1

- COFUND Actions

The EU funding rate for COFUND actions varies based on joint funding with national governments, industry, or other bodies. There are two main types:

- i) ERA-NET Cofund: supports public-public partnerships and joint programming initiatives.
- ii) European Joint Programme (EJP) Cofund: supports coordinated national research and innovation programmes.

- Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP)^{36 37}

- Scope: encourages public purchase of R&D services of pivotal solutions to improve public sector quality and efficiency.
- Funding: reimbursement of coordination and networking activities should not exceed 30%. Indirect costs are calculated as a 25% flat rate of direct costs.

- Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI)³⁸

- Scope: early deployment of innovative solutions addressing public interest challenges.
- Funding: reimbursement of coordination and networking activities should not exceed 50%. Indirect costs are calculated as a 25% flat rate of direct costs.

2. Eligibility and Application³⁹

To be eligible for Horizon Europe funding, projects must involve at least three partner institutions from eligible countries. Applications are submitted through the European Commission's [Funding and tenders portal](#), where you can find calls for proposals, topics, deadlines, and application forms.

To apply, create a profile on the portal, select the relevant call, and use the online form to submit your proposal before the deadline. Some calls have a two-stage application process: first submit a concept note, and if successful, then draft and submit the full proposal.

After the application period closes, the proposals are evaluated by expert panels according to European Commission criteria. The evaluation phase can last up to 5 months. Successful applicants are then notified, and a grant agreement is prepared, detailing the project's activities, duration, budget, and terms. This agreement is typically signed within 3 months.

Additional Information. Detailed descriptions of action types are available in the [General Annexes](#) of the Main Work Programme and the [ERC Work Programme](#).

³⁶ More information available at:

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/new-european-innovation-agenda/innovation-procurement/pre-commercial-procurement_en

³⁷ For more information, see the Frequently Asked Questions on PCP and PPI: <http://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/redirection/document/5207>

³⁸ More information available at:

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/new-european-innovation-agenda/innovation-procurement/public-procurement-innovative-solutions_en

³⁹ For detailed information on who should apply and the general conditions for Horizon Europe, please refer to the European Commission's guidelines available at: https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-who-should-apply_en

European Innovation Council Fund scheme

The EIC Fund is the investment branch of the European Commission's EIC Accelerator programme, aimed at backing high-risk, market-creating innovations in the deep tech sector. With a budget of €3 billion for 2021-2027, it aspires to become one of Europe's leading deep-tech venture capitalists, providing essential investment to startups and scale-ups.

The investment process includes nine steps, starting with communication, due diligence, and compliance checks. This is followed by the EIB preparing an investment recommendation for review by the investment committee and Board of Directors. The final steps involve issuing a term sheet and signing the investment agreement.

For high-risk projects not ready for private investment, the EIC Fund uses convertible notes, which offer a debt feature with the option to convert into equity. The EIC Fund evaluates lead and co-investors based on eight criteria outlined in its Investment Guidelines, with assessments made on a case-by-case basis.

The EIC Fund typically relies on valuations set by private co-investors rather than conducting its own valuations. It primarily invests through equity or quasi-equity, emphasising substantial support for high-potential innovations.

EIC funding opportunities

❖ **EIC Pathfinder**^{40 41}

EIC Pathfinder overview

The EIC Pathfinder is a funding programme within Horizon Europe designed to support research teams in the following ways:

- Funding breakthrough research: provides financial support to develop the scientific foundation needed for groundbreaking technologies.
- Supporting early-stage R&D: helps with the initial stages of research and development in scientific, technological, or deep-tech areas.
- Encouraging innovation: focuses on new, cutting-edge scientific and technological directions to disrupt existing fields or create new market opportunities.
- Realising technological solutions: aims to develop and scale up innovative technologies and disruptive innovations across Europe.

Grant funding details

Grants of up to 3 to 4 million euro to support early stage development of future technologies (e.g. various activities at low TRL 1-3), up to proof of concept.

⁴⁰ Find out more about the EIC Pathfinder funding programme at: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-pathfinder_en

⁴¹ Browse the frequently asked questions: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-frequently-asked-questions_en#eic-pathfinder

- Pathfinder Challenges - grants of up to EUR 4 million or more if duly justified
- Pathfinder Open - grants of up to EUR 3 million or more if duly justified

Pathfinder projects can also receive additional funding for testing the innovation potential of their research outputs.

❖ **EIC Transition**^{42 43}

EIC Transition overview

The EIC Transition is a funding programme under Horizon Europe targeting innovation activities that goes beyond the experimental proof of principle in the laboratory. It supports both the maturation and validation of novel technologies from the lab to the relevant application environments.

The EIC Transition offers support to SMEs, start-ups, and organisations that:

- Identify promising results: have EU-funded project results with strong commercial potential that could lead to new innovations and business opportunities.
- Advance novel technologies: possess novel technologies ready for further development and validation for high-potential commercial applications.
- Conduct market research: have performed preliminary market research to identify potential markets and competitors for their innovation.
- Build a strong team: plan to assemble a motivated and entrepreneurial team with diverse skills, including researchers, business experts, and marketers, to drive the idea towards commercial success.

Grant funding details

- Main Grants: up to €2.5 million to validate and demonstrate technology in relevant application environments (starting at TRL 3/4 and aiming for TRL 5/6) and to develop business and market readiness.
- Booster Grants: fixed amounts up to €50,000 to support complementary activities that explore commercialization pathways or for portfolio activities.

❖ **EIC Accelerator**^{44 45}

EIC Accelerator overview

The EIC Accelerator is a funding programme under Horizon Europe designed to support the development and scaling up of innovations with the potential to create new markets or

⁴² Find out more about the EIC Transition funding programme at: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-transition_en

⁴³ Browse the frequently asked questions: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-frequently-asked-questions_en

⁴⁴ Find out more about the EIC Transition funding programme at: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-funding-opportunities/eic-accelerator_en

⁴⁵ Browse the frequently asked questions: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-frequently-asked-questions_en

disrupt existing ones. It provides assistance to start-ups and SMEs in advancing their technologies from the laboratory stage to commercial deployment.

The EIC Accelerator offers support to:

- i) Start-ups and SMEs: businesses and individuals aiming to launch or grow a small to medium-sized enterprise.
- ii) Small Mid-Caps: companies seeking equity investment.

Grant funding details

- Main Grants: up to €2.5 million for innovation activities (TRL 5-8), focusing on technology development to be completed within 24 months. Grants are available for projects aiming to reach TRL 8 and continue further development independently.
- Equity Investments: up to €15 million for market deployment (TRL 9), based on the "patient capital" principle with a 7-10 year investment horizon.
- Blended finance: a combination of non-dilutive grants for innovation (TRL 5-8) and dilutive equity for market deployment (TRL 9).
- Investment only: For mid-cap companies or those that have received "grant only" funding.

LIFE Programme Funding scheme

The LIFE Programme⁴⁶ offers various types of grants to support a wide range of environmental and climate initiatives.

1. LIFE sub-programmes

- *Nature and Biodiversity*: the [Nature and Biodiversity](#) sub-programme will aim at the protection and restoration of Europe's nature and halting and reversing biodiversity loss. So, the LIFE Nature and Biodiversity sub-programme will continue to fund nature conservation projects, in particular in the areas of biodiversity, habitats, and species.
- *Circular economy and quality of life*: the [Circular economy and quality of life](#) sub-programme aims at facilitating the transition toward a sustainable, circular, toxic-free, energy-efficient and climate-resilient economy and at protecting, restoring and improving the quality of the environment, either through direct interventions or by supporting the integration of those objectives in other policies. Thus, LIFE will continue to co-finance projects in the environmental sector, in particular in the area of the circular economy, including recovery of resources from waste, water, air, noise, soil, and chemical management as well as environmental governance.
- *Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation*: the [Climate Change Mitigation and Adaptation](#) sub-programme will contribute to the shift towards a sustainable, energy-efficient, renewable

⁴⁶ Browse the frequently asked questions:
https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/document/download/de1b1727-d889-4527-9415-0da84af3f7d2_en?filename=FAQs_LIFE-2024-Calls.pdf

energy-based, climate-neutral and resilient economy, thereby contributing to sustainable development. The LIFE programme co-finances projects in the areas of urban adaptation and land-use planning, resilience of infrastructure, sustainable management of water in drought-prone areas, flood and coastal management, resilience of the agricultural, forestry and tourism sectors, and/or support to the EU's outermost regions: preparedness for extreme weather events, notably in coastal areas.

- *Clean Energy Transition*: the LIFE [Clean Energy Transition](#) sub-programme aims to support the shift towards an energy-efficient, renewable energy-based, climate-neutral and resilient economy. It funds coordination and support actions across Europe, targeting market barriers to sustainable energy and involving a range of stakeholders, including SMEs, local and regional public authorities, non-profit organisations, and consumers.

2. Eligibility and Application

The LIFE Programme is open to public or private legal entities registered in the EU or its overseas countries or territories, third countries associated with the LIFE Programme, and legal entities established under Union law or international organisations. However, natural persons are not eligible to apply. Legal entities from non-associated third countries may participate if necessary to achieve the objectives of a specific action, but they generally must bear the cost of their participation.

Applications for the LIFE Programme must be submitted through the [Funding & Tender opportunities portal](#).

Project proposals submitted under LIFE calls are evaluated and scored against specific selection and award criteria to ensure they meet the programme's quality and relevance standards.

National contact points (NCP)⁴⁷ are available to assist with applications, organise information and networking events, and offer proposal writing workshops. They also support the communication and dissemination of project results.

European Regional Development Fund overview

1. Funding Priorities (2021-2027)

- **Competitiveness and Innovation**: Supports small and medium-sized businesses, digitisation, and digital connectivity.
- **Sustainability and Low-Carbon Economy**: Focuses on creating a greener and more resilient Europe.
- **Connectivity**: Enhances mobility across the EU.
- **Social Inclusion**: Promotes employment, education, social inclusion, equal access to healthcare, and cultural and sustainable tourism.
- **Local Development**: Supports locally led and sustainable urban development.

⁴⁷ For more information, visit the https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life/life-european-countries_en

2. Application and Eligibility

The ERDF is accessible to a wide range of entities, including public bodies, private sector organisations (especially small businesses), universities, associations, NGOs, voluntary organisations, and foreign firms that have a base in the region and comply with European public procurement rules.

- ★ *Application process.* To apply for funding, applicants must submit their proposals to the managing authority* of the relevant regional programme. This authority⁴⁸ is responsible for evaluating the applications and making funding decisions.
- ★ *Project requirements.* Projects seeking funding must align with the selection criteria and investment priorities⁴⁹ of the regional programme. There is no minimum size for projects; what matters is their European added value, their impact on employment, their innovative nature, and their contribution to regional economic competitiveness.

For guidance and assistance, advice and support can be obtained from several sources, including [Europe Direct information relays](#), managing authorities, European teams within local authorities or chambers of commerce, and the [Enterprise Europe Network](#).

Innovation Fund overview

To date, the Innovation Fund has awarded €6.5 billion to over 100 projects across EU member states and the EEA countries (Liechtenstein, Iceland, and Norway). The programme focuses on breakthrough technologies and large-scale flagship projects that offer substantial European added value.

The range of supported technologies is broad, including those related to energy-intensive industries, renewables, energy storage, net-zero mobility, hydrogen, and carbon capture, use, and storage. By prioritising projects with significant greenhouse gas reduction potential, the Innovation Fund aims to drive progress towards a climate-neutral and resilient Europe.

- *Calls - regular grants*⁵⁰. The IF awards grants through calls for proposals and [competitive bidding procedures \(auctions\)](#). The Fund aims to finance a varied project pipeline achieving an optimal balance of a wide range of innovative technologies in all eligible sectors (energy intensive industries, renewable energy, energy storage, carbon, capture, use and storage, and net-zero mobility and buildings) in EU Member States, Iceland, Norway, and Liechtenstein. At the same time, the projects need to be sufficiently mature in terms of planning, business model, and financial and legal structure.
- *Auctions*⁵¹. The IF awards grants through calls for proposals and auctions (competitive bidding). The IF runs auctions to provide cost-efficient support to renewable fuel of non-biological origin

⁴⁸ Find here the related managing authority: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/in-your-country/managing-authorities_en

⁴⁹ Check here the European operational programmes in the pertinent region: https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/in-your-country/programmes_en

⁵⁰ Find out more information about grants at: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/innovation-fund/calls-regular-grants_en

⁵¹ Find out more information about auctions at: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/innovation-fund/auctions_en

(RFNBO) hydrogen producers within the European Union and the European Economic Area. It will kick-start the development of a European hydrogen market and contribute to meeting Europe's ambitious climate targets.

Support for applicants

- ★ Tools and Guidelines⁵². Calculate the greenhouse gas emission avoidance potential of your project using provided tools and guidelines.
- ★ National Info Days⁵³. Stay informed about upcoming Innovation Fund info days in various EU countries.
- ★ Project Development Assistance⁵⁴. Receive tailored support from the EIB to enhance your project's maturity.
- ★ National Contact Points⁵⁵. Access personal support and advice in your country.

⁵² Available online at: https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/innovation-fund/tools-and-guidance_en

⁵³ Available online at: https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-funding-climate-action/innovation-fund/events-and-webinars_en

⁵⁴ Available online at: https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-funding-climate-action/innovation-fund/project-development-assistance_en

⁵⁵ Available online at: https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/eu-funding-climate-action/innovation-fund/national-contact-points_en

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